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Family life in Uzbekistan*

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ga tayyorlashning psixologik
muammolari*

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YOUTH PREPARATION FOR FAMILY LIFE IN UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation. *It is important to have a clear understanding of this concept when considering how important information security is to the existing society and determining the budget to ensure it. This is the only way to determine the priorities and create an appropriate action plan. Information security in networks involves a wide range of problems. Information security is the basis of public welfare, so we will consider all the problems it solves in detail. This article provides an evidence-based analysis of information security issues and legal and technical measures to address them, as well as recommendations for individuals to ensure their information security.*

Keywords: *information security, information protection, IT infrastructure, network, methods of network hacking, Communication, Telecommunication, state system, constitutional norm.*

The topic of family life education in Uzbekistan and surrounding regions has drawn considerable attention in scholarly research, with varying perspectives. While the existence of studies addressing the issue, a lack of direct matches with our specific theme has led us to categorize available similar research. Within the first category, religious literature has dominated the discussion, particularly due to the prominent influence of Islam in the region. The second category includes graduate school studies that examine the topic through various angles, with a particular focus on the intended outcomes of the research. The third cluster comprises manuals and textbooks developed by professionals, providing a comprehensive examination of family relationships.

Starting from Uzbek religious sources it is necessary to mention one of the well-known manuscript entitled "Happy Family", authored by Shaikh Muhammad Sodik Muhammad Yusuf. This book aims to educate Muslim youth on how to establish a harmonious family life in accordance with Islamic laws, commonly referred to as "Sharia"¹. The book emphasizes the importance of marriage in Islam, citing numerous hadiths (sayings of the Prophet Muhammad S.A.V.) and verses from the Quran that demonstrate the early Muslim leaders' quick remarriage after the death of their spouses or divorce.

The book offers practical guidance to Muslim households on raising children, maintaining a good relationship with relatives, and creating a positive family atmosphere. These recommendations are founded on religious teachings, with each section using religious examples to illustrate the ways to achieve marital happiness. However, the author does not delve into the specific details or nature of potential challenges that families might face, preferring instead to provide broad-based guidance and a religious approach to problem solving. Undoubtedly, this book offers valuable insights to Muslims seeking guidance on creating a happy family. However, it may not be a suitable resource for secular educational institutions, given the diversity of cultural, ethnic and religious backgrounds of social groups. Additionally, those who do not adhere to Sharia law may be less inclined to follow suggestions and solutions that rely on religious doctrine.

In summary, "Happy Family" is a helpful guide for Muslim families seeking to build a strong foundation for their lives based on Sharia, offering practical advice and using religious examples to illustrate the path to happiness. However, it may not be as relevant to non-religious audiences or those who do not prioritize religious teachings in family life.

Another similar volume is "Preparing Youth for Family Life" authored by Muminjon Saydaliev.

¹ Shayx Muxammad Sodik Muhammad Yusuf. Baxtiyor oila. - Toshkent: «Hilol-Nashr», 2013. – B. 175.

Although it is not scientific research in a secular sense, it is a valuable resource for preparing for family life according to Sharia. The book is heavily influenced by the Quran and the sayings of the Prophet Muhammad (S.A.V.) and serves as an excellent guide in the family preparation of young people, especially teens.

The book covers a wide range of topics related to family life, including specific rules for naming children, the first steps in education after birth, physical exercise, raising girls, good behavior, modesty, contentment, and a professional career. There are sections directly deal with the family life education, including medical examination, rules for declaring marriage, and the allocation of funds to a wife. Final parts of the book dedicated to familial responsibilities and recommendations for mother in laws, wives, and women. The book stresses the importance of love in family life and offers guidance on finding a good spouse, as well as advice on maintaining healthy family relationships. This book is a popular source of knowledge among the Muslim population of Uzbekistan and neighboring countries, despite the fact that it is not included in the curriculum of schools and universities. Nonetheless, real explanation of marital life details did this source very readable even among nonreligious people.

One of the best studies with historical background is "Oila" ("Family") by Abdurauf Fitrat, one of the famous representatives of the Jadid movement in Central Asia. Fitrat analyses different aspects of family such as necessity of marriage, number of wives, how to choose a wife, important thing for potential wife and husband before the marriage, how to organize the wedding and mahr² payment peculiarities, sexual relations of marital life, children education, physical education, moral education, school, girls education, parental rights, orphanage rights, servant rights etc.

According to the author, every Muslim requires to have a family, and get married as soon as possible after reaching puberty. To prove his assumption, the author cites numerous ideas taken from the Holy Book of the Qur'an and Hadith, which convince of the need for family and family run. The interesting point of this study is the comparison of France, Germany and Great Britain in the 19th century, and how their demography dispersed from each other during one century while at the beginning of the century the population was almost the same. The population

of France increased 11 million during 80 90 years, but of Great Britain increased from 52 million and France 41 million people. The main reason for this difference was the attitude towards the family in these countries. According to the author, growth of nation was one of the main missions of Great Britain. Coming from this fact author assumes, that every Muslim has to create a family for the sake of Islam and make babies as many as possible to serve Islam. This study was interesting for my study because the author eagerly recommends making babies as many as possible since it is a religious mission³.

There are many nonreligious studies of Uzbek researchers focused to explore different aspects of youth preparation for matrimony. Now we will review on the Uzbek scholarly works and post-graduate investigations, which focused on the youth education for family relations. For example, M.Ismatullaeva focuses on psychological aspects of family life education⁴. The author discusses socio-psychological issues related to the family based the views of medieval oriental thinkers and modern approaches. In his opinion, the question of a person's readiness for marriage and family life is a very complex indicator, having an individual character that cannot be measured by any strict standards. All of the above shows that the factors of premarital marriage are among the most difficult problems. This means that for all educational institutions (schools, lyceums, colleges, institutes), final exams (the system of state examinations, thesis defense systems, etc.) determine maturity, that is, the readiness of a young person for an independent life. This gives them a certain right to the fact that they can subsequently continue their education or work in a certain specialty. From this point of view, "maturity" serves as an indicator that determines the qualitative and quantitative characteristics of achieving a certain stage, phase, limit of development with a certain accuracy. The author points out that this stage indicates readiness for family life.

The next article "Responsibilities for preparing young people for family life"⁵ by D.Toshtemirova argues living in a family is of great importance in youth education for family relations, and emphasizes the responsibility of parents in raising young people to create their own family in the future.

Throughout their lives, children receive a lot of

² Mahr is the mandatory gift that the husband gives to his wife at the wedding. / <https://nikahforever.com/blog/mahr-in-islam/>

³ Fitrat Abdurauf, Oila yoki Oilani Boshqarish tartiblari / A.Fitrat; tarjimon va izohlar muallifi Sh Vohidov; - Toshkent. Cho'pon nomidagi NMIU, 2013 – 144 b.

⁴ Ismatillayeva M.M. Yuqori sinf o'quvchilarini oilaviy hayotga tarbiyalashning pedagogic psixologik jihatlari

// Conference papers. 2022

⁵ Toshtemirova D. Yoshlarni oilaviy hayotga tayyorlash majburiyatlari // International Conference on Developments in Education. <https://econferenczone.org>. April 25th 2022. – 151 b.

information from older generation about attitudes towards members of the opposite sex; learn about marriage, family, and norms of behavior. They develop early feelings such as camaraderie, friendship, pride and duty. While all of these are valuable, in our fast-paced lives today, they rarely come naturally. For this reason, the author puts forward the conclusion that the task of special family life education should be assigned primarily to the school and family. Nevertheless, the article does not propose any serious mechanism for school curriculum.

One of the articles closer to our research issue is "The Importance of Pre- Wedding Factors in Preventing Divorce and Influencing Family Cohesion" by A.Kovlonbekov. In the article author highlights the central role of prewedding factors that contribute to disputes and separation in families. He emphasizes the significance of women's relationships in the family, particularly between the mother-in-law and the bride, and proposes that pre-wedding family life education can prevent these issues. The author observes that women often enter their husband's family with negative impressions of their mother-in-law, leading to negative reactions to any comments made by their mother-in-law. As a result, conflicts between husbands and wives can stem from this strained relationship between the two women. However, if the mother-in-law and the bride have a good relationship, the family is likely to live peacefully. The author further suggests that young people often overestimate their abilities and lack sufficient preparation for family life. He advocates for more education and support for young brides and their families to promote a harmonious family life⁶.

There are two identical articles of Uzbek researchers on psychological aspects of youth education for a family life with almost same title: "Psychological properties of preparing young people for family life"⁷. First article is of two lecturers A.Dawkeeva, K.Kemalbaev from the Nukus State Pedagogic University, and the second article is of Abdusamatova Sh. by senior lecturer of the Chirchik State Pedagogic University. The second article also gives a general idea of the psychological aspects of preparing for family life. From the volume of articles, it can be assumed that both of them were written by young researchers to identify their interest in this issue. They are both very short, the first is only four pages and the second is seven pages, and both

do not set out to analyze thoroughly or solve any specific scientific problem. Both articles examine the necessary psychological attitudes and conditions for marriage and maintaining family relationships. According to the authors, it is psychological readiness, or rather education, that is the key to solving many family issues.

One of the interesting studies is a monograph by Muratova Sh, "Socio-psychological features of preparing boys for life in a family"⁸. This book is a valuable resource that examines the challenges in family education, focusing on boys' perspectives. The author provides an in-depth exploration of the various aspects of family planning and the factors that impact young men's preferences for potential brides. Through surveys performed among young people, the book reveals that most boys desire to marry girls from successful families, as well as those who are beautiful and educated. Although the survey results did not reveal any unexpected or unusual answers, it is likely that the young men surveyed were well prepared for such a questionnaire. The standardized and expected responses suggest that the subjects were well briefed and had an understanding of the desired answers. This indicates that the results of the survey may not fully reflect the opinions and attitudes of all boys, and that more research may need to be conducted to gain a complete understanding of their perspectives.

Despite the author's exclusion of controversial attitudes toward girls, this monograph is a valuable asset for researchers and academics alike. It serves as a comprehensive account of the subject matter and provides a foundation for future studies on similar topics. In addition, the limited availability of such literature in Uzbekistan suggests a need for greater dissemination and exposure to these types of resources.

Although it is widely believed that there are no official textbooks on family psychology specifically designed for older high schools, academic lyceums, and technical colleges in Uzbekistan, this is not entirely accurate. There is a textbook "Family Psychology" by F. Akramova is a comprehensive guide to understand teen family life education. This book is edited by well-known professor G.Shoumarov covers many topics of adolescent development, from the physiological changes during puberty to their psychological transformation. We will stop to the information in the book, which is interesting for our investigation. According to the

⁶ Qovlonbekov A. Oilaviy ajrimlarni oldini olishda nikoh oldi omillarining ahamiyati va oila mustahkamligiga ta'siri // Международный научный журнал «Новости образования: исследование в XXI веке» № 9 (100), часть 3, апрель, 2023 г. – В. 1490 -1497.

⁷ Abdusmatova Sh. Yoshlarni oilaviy hayotga tayyorlashning psixologik xususiyatlari. // Fan, ta'lim va amaliyot integratsiyasi. Jild 02, Nashr 02, Yanvar. 2021.

⁸ Муратова Ш.Н. Ўғил болаларни оилага тайёрлашнинг ижтимоий-психологик хусусиятлари. Монография. Самарканд. "СамДТЧИ" нашриёти, 2023. - 118 б.

information in the book, it is approved by the Ministry of Higher Education and designed for school and college education, includes all topics regarding family relationships.

The next information is, that “this textbook is intended for students of academic lyceums and vocational colleges and, as a test textbook created for the first time, is somewhat different from other traditional textbooks on this topic”.

The last interesting information is, that “the creation of the course “Family Psychology” and its inclusion in the schedule of classes in schools, colleges and lyceums among academic subjects is a logical and meaningful continuation of the active social policy pursued by the government of our Republic”. According to the above information, the textbook approved by the ministry and introduced into the education system.

However, this textbook appears to be unfinished due to some grammatical errors found in the e-book. Additionally, the book was not been published officially, which raises questions about its validity. Usually if textbook approved by the Ministry of Higher Education published officially, it excludes any grammatical mistakes, and published with all the necessary information, including the names of the authors, editors, reviewers, university, and department’s protocol number.

Nevertheless, this free book in eBook format gives enough information for students and researchers. During the research, we have to identify curriculum of high schools and colleges in order to determine the textbooks, including “Family Psychology” by F. Akramova. On the other hand, it is interesting to investigate the reasons for the existence of the unofficial e-format of this book on the Internet and the refusal of the published format of this book in schools and colleges⁹.

One of this researcher’s recent publications, “Preparation of Youth for Family Life in Education System – as a Current Issue,” is a closer publication in our study. However, the article aims at studying the opinions of young people in relation to the family. The main point of this study is that the author conducted a survey among young male military personnel, whose idea of family is very connected with their profession. Not without reason, the survey results showed that about 68% of all respondents claimed that they had some kind of knowledge about family and family relationships¹⁰. It is hard to confirm the validity of such investigation, since according to our field studies and observations there are many

officers among military personnel who do not feel marital satisfaction.

The next book is “Strengthening reproductive health and forming a healthy lifestyle in preparing girls for family life” by collective of authors. This publication dedicated to the Year of Health in Uzbekistan. This book is under edition of Associate Prof. S.Tursunov, and written by Prof. D.D. Sharipova, Assoc. Prof. S.T. Tursunov, Assoc. Prof. O.R. Jamoldinova, Assoc. Prof. G.A. Shakhmurova. This is a manual which was published by the decision of the meeting of the Center for Promoting a Healthy Lifestyle “Oydin Hayot” dated November 21, 2013 No. 12.

This manual is a very important source for preparing young girls for family life in terms of leading a healthy lifestyle. The book includes general topics that define the human health system as a whole and a healthy lifestyle.

In addition, there are many specific topics related to preserving and promoting the health of teenage girls. Since the manual aims educating female adolescents only, it can be classified as not primary textbook, but additional material used in educational institutions. It should be noted that although the authors of this publication are university researchers, the book was published on behalf of NGOs. In our opinion, this also strengthens the advisory rather than obligatory nature of the source¹¹.

One of the significant publications is monograph by M.Abdullaeva “Spiritual Preparation of Teens for Family Life”. According to the information given in the book, it dedicated to the “Year of Strong Family”, which published in 2012. According to the information of author, the book is for parents, researchers, and the people interested in this topic and accordingly this monograph is recommendatory by nature. The structure and main ideas of the book give reason to believe that the author provides general data on the preparation of young people in the field of their spiritual education. Author does not set himself the disclosure of any scientific problems related to the problems of spiritual training of young people. In addition, the book does not provide statistical or other official data regarding the growth or decline in the spiritual preparation of young people. Apparently, there is no intention of the author to criticize the spiritual education system. However, the book contents general negative aspects of spiritual and moral decay¹².

There are some high school programs in other post-soviet countries on the family preparation. One

⁹ Акрамова Ф. Оила психологияси / Г.Шоумаров тахрири остида. 2011. – 244 б.

¹⁰ Акрамова Ф.А, Билолова З.Б. Таълим тизимида ёшларни оилавий ҳаётга тайёрлаш – долзарб муаммо сифатида // Замонавий таълим, 2018, № 9.

¹¹ Қизларни оилавий ҳаётга тайёрлашда репродуктив саломатлигини мустаҳкамлаш ва соғлом турмуш тарзини шакллантириш. –Т.: «Fan va texnologiya», 2014, - 112 б.

of them called “Basics of Family Life: Preparation for Marriage and Family Life: 9th grade” by V.V.Martinova, E.K.Pogodina, which is taught in secondary education of the Republic of Belarus. This program contains elective classes developed for students of the 9-11th grade of general secondary educational institutions. This is a perfectly designed program, which covers culture of relationships between boys and girls, psychophysiological characteristics of boys and girls, behavior of boys and girls, reproductive health of youth, love in a person’s life, preparation for future family life, readiness for marriage and family life, motives for marriage, secrets of family happiness etc. It also considers issues related to early marriages, early pregnancy, and divorces. Overall, this textbook is an excellent resource for high school students, which can and should be recommended for Uzbek schools¹³.

The next article by well-known Russian scholar Dubrovina I. V. entitled “Preparing youth for family life, or “Forgotten” self-determination,”¹⁴ directly relates to our problems and is aimed at revealing the psychological aspects of preparing youth for family relationships. According to author, one of the key aspects of self-determination of a growing person is the psychological formation of a person and readiness for family life. I.Dubrovina substantiates the need to increase the spiritual and moral level. If psychological development of a child by adolescence is not sufficient, sexuality will conflict with higher emotions and aspirations. The problem of “sex education” lies not only in “family studies” lessons, and in an emphasis on sexual relationships, but also, most importantly, in the development of personal qualities necessary to create a prosperous and happy family.

The author supports her arguments with insights from famous thinkers who perfectly outlined the importance of psychological education to succeed in family relations. Many thinkers such as L.N. Tolstoy, L.Feuerbach, K. Marx, Engels, V. Sukhomlinsky, and others ideally pointed out the importance of different aspects of early family education. Here we have quoted from V.Sukhomlinsky, who unmistakably points out the need to create a family based on love, which in his opinion leads to personal happiness and further the happiness of the entire society. “The most difficult page of human wisdom is to comprehend with the mind and heart what it means to love so that

the one you love is happy so that the one whom love gives birth to comes into the world happy. Not only personal happiness depends on how the younger generations master this great wisdom. The moral purity and happiness of the entire society depends on this.”¹⁵ The textbook of I.Dubrovina as well as the Belarusian textbook, is a very useful source of knowledge for schools and lyceums.

It is interesting to review Japanese sources, since youth education for marriage in Japan is extremely interesting in terms of comparison. The Japanese government has paid attention to the importance of educating school students to the family roles and responsibilities. In 1947, the Japanese Ministry of Education mandated that students from both genders were trained to play their family roles and obligations, focusing on home economics departments. This mandatory education sought to enhance the lives of families by equipping students with the necessary skills and knowledge required for family life, beginning from grade 5. The curriculum revision in 2002 reinforced the importance of education for students in grades 5 and 6, emphasizing knowledge, skill acquisition, interest in daily familial circumstances, and family life as a family member. Textbooks approved by the Japanese government tend to focus on normative family requirements and the ideal family life, which may not necessarily reflect the reality of some students’ lives¹⁶.

In Japan, family life topics are extensively covered in various subjects at the upper-secondary level, particularly in the Home Economics department. This content has been mandated for girls since 1960, and later incorporated into the curriculum for both boys and girls in 1989. Additionally, the secondary school subjects “Life Environment Studies” and “Morals” also include similar material related to family interaction, ethics, and family and society. According to the Ministry of Education of Japan, these subjects aid students in learning about human development, daily life, the meaning of families, and family and community connections. Moreover, the mandate of family life topics by the Ministry of Education of Japan is consistent across subjects. These topics are extensively covered in the Home Economics department, while students are also expected to acquire knowledge and skills for daily life and understand human development in Life Environment Studies and Morals. Notably,

¹² М. Абдуллаева. Ўсмирларни оилавий ҳаётга маънавий тайёрлаш. Монография. –Т.: «Fan va texnologiya», 2012, - 116 б.

¹³ Мартынова, В. В. Основы семейной жизни: Подготовка к браку и семейной жизни: 9-й класс: пособие для педагогов учреждений общего среднего образования с белорусским и русским языками обучения / В. В. Мартынова, Е. К. Погодина. – Минск: Национальный институт образования, 2020. — 192 с.

¹⁴ Дубровина И.В. «Подготовка молодежи к семейной жизни, или «Забытое» самоопределение» // Вестник практической психологии образования. Том 12. № 3. (44) июль – сентябрь. 2015. – С. 17–23.

¹⁵ Сухомилинский В.А. Рождение гражданина. – М., 1971. – С.43.

¹⁶ Family Life Education During Childhood // family.jrank.org/pages/541

cooperatively creating family and community life between men and women is a key goal across these subjects, and this content is further reinforced¹⁷.

One of the studies of Japanese researcher's group is called "Is Family Life Education at school in Japan effective for Japanese fathers?: Focusing on Co- educational Home Economics Education and Intention to Do Household Work". This study aims to analyze the results of the Survey on "Time Use and Leisure Activities" conducted by the Statistics Bureau of Japan in 2016. This analysis aims to examine the role of the father in the family, in terms of time for completing family tasks and caring for children. The study gives a comparative analysis table of Japanese fathers with European ones, on devoting time to family tasks. The value of this study is that authors point out that there are following subjects to prepare students for family in Japanese schools: Home Economics Education (HEE) and Family Life Education (FLE).

The results of the study show that the subjects are useful for students, and the subject FLE provides primary and general information about family relationships. Another study by the Japan Association of Home Economics Education finds that students are trained to perform family tasks such as sewing and cooking, although hours for these classes are limited. This study indicates an insufficiency of general understanding of family life to acquire household working skills and traditional gender roles in the family. Consequently, limited school education in these subjects does not provide enough knowledge of household running.

One of the interesting points of this study is that the promotion of traditional gender roles and the effectiveness of the FLE subject are not entirely compatible. To substantiate this idea, the idea is given that gender roles are different in the family and in society. Since FLE in Japan has long been intended for girls, there is now a need to improve the program to include boys. In addition, school education is not enough to fully represent the family environment. Authors conclude, in order to full preparation of students in high schools, it is necessary to test them in different life circumstances outside of school¹⁸.

"Family Relationships and Adolescent Development in Japan: A Family - Systems Perspective on the Japanese Family" is one of the extended analyses made by Hiroshi Shimizu¹⁹. This study of Japanese author as previous, indicated important moments of family relations in Japan.

According to the author, Japanese mother plays central role in socialization of children. Japanese parents intensely care about the children, however adolescents try to seek emotional ties outside the families. Japanese families prefer not to express disagreements between spouses.

There are a lot of similarities between Japanese and Uzbek families in terms of mother-son and father-son relations, according to the study. Mothers are mostly responsible for the education of children in Japan, and ties between mother and son remains as strong even after the son being married. This tie keeps during entire life of them. Remoteness of fathers from the family due to jobs, distancing factor of relations between sons and fathers. However, Japanese adolescents try to get independent from mothers, which is also similar Uzbek young people.

Literature review conclusion. A review of the literature of researchers in Uzbekistan and neighboring countries allows us to highlight certain points. Most researchers clearly believe that family happiness based on the spiritual and psychological development of a young people. This means that a prosperous family is a union of two people of the opposite sex who brought up with high moral values. However, most literature does not examine family problems and the causes of family discord. Moreover, most authors do not consider details and stages of family formation, significant part of young families created without psychological preparation, countless couples psychologically incompatible to each other.

First category of studies are religious in character. Sources of a religious nature are largely narrative in nature, although the main ideas and recommendations based on religious books such as the Qur'an and Hadith. These books are largely advisory in nature, many of which deliberately omit family problems arising from failed relationships. In other words, it can be assumed authors of religious studies prefer not to delve into the details of family issues; instead, they strongly recommend religious training to avoid future marital conflicts and divorces.

The study of religious literature gives serious reason to believe that the happiest, most stable families in Muslim society are families created based on Sharia. For family stability, religious training of young people is significant. Many disagreements between a man and a woman ensured precisely by Sharia rules. Coming out from religious literature we assume, that family satisfaction reached if all members of marriage follow sharia rules, educated

¹⁷ Family Life Education During Adolescence// family.jrank.org/pages/542

¹⁸ Kurokawa Kinuyo, Takahashi Keiko, Kuramoto Ayako. Is Family Life Education at school in Japan effective for Japanese fathers?: Focusing on Coeducational Home Economics Education and Intention to Do Household Work // Research Bulletin of Naruto University of Education. Volume 35, 2020.

¹⁹ Per Gjerde, Hiroshi Shimizu "Family Relationships and Adolescent Development in Japan: A Family Systems Perspective on the Japanese Family" // Journal of Research on Adolescence 5(3):281-318. July 1995.

according to sharia. When religiosity of society is diverse and sharia law is not applicable in post-soviet countries, preparation of families is secular in most, and therefore it cannot be evaluated in the context of religion. On the other hand, it is not easy religious studies classified as scholarly research while operating with secular scientific principles. Although religious sources are very popular among the people and have very useful content from the point of view of preparing young people for family relationships.

Summarizing sources of a secular nature, most of which belong to professional researchers and professors of higher educational institutions, it can be argued that education for family life in schools has not been successful in Uzbekistan. We can even safely say that the school curriculum simply does not include subjects in this area. There have been many attempts to include the subject "Family Psychology" in the school curriculum; programs in this area have been approved by the Ministry of Public Education. After these programs and subjects were not implemented in practice, they were redirected to other broader programs like "Spirituality and Enlightenment." In a word, sources indicate that the problem of preparing for a family has always been relevant in society. Scientists and researchers have addressed this topic constantly. They analyzed family problems quite carefully, and proposed various options for training young people in colleges and lyceums, excluding high schools. However, we were unable to come across studies that tried to find the reasons for the exclusion of family education subjects from the school curriculum in secondary schools in Uzbekistan. The authors provide analyzes about the need for these subjects for schoolchildren, point out the problems of young families, while keeping silent about the reasons for the lack of family education subjects.

Originality. This study is the first to examine family preparation necessity, addressing to a non-educational context. This study differs from others in that the author looks at the problem of society from the point of view of the increase in divorce. Based on the analysis of the problem of rising divorces, the author comes to the conclusion that family life education in Uzbekistan is necessary for the younger generation. Speaking about the format of preparation for the family, this study examines all aspects, including school education, family education and mahalla education. We have not encountered this format for studying the problem of preparing young people for family life in other studies.

In the process of studying this issue, we came to the conclusion that in Uzbekistan, scientists and

researchers studying this issue can be grouped and classified. First of all, researchers are divided into scientific, religious, spiritual and educational and teaching. Scientific research, according to our observations, partially examines the problem of preparing young people for family relationships. Among the studies, we found many good studies that discuss the problem of preparing adolescents for an independent family life.

The next category, that is, religious researchers, although they imply problems of family relationships, do not discuss them in the books and place the main emphasis on recommendations to parents in preparing their sons and daughters in order to avoid family disagreements in the future.

Very widespread publications, articles and books devoted to this topic, from the point of view of narrative presentation and from the point of view of purpose, can be classified as spiritual and educational in nature. Such researchers, mainly from the spiritual and educational spheres, are many poets and writers. Their publications are largely narrative in nature, they do not set themselves the goal of scientific analysis, and in their opinion, the younger generation needs to be raised in accordance with national traditions, religious canons, and subsequently they will create a strong family. Although in the middle of the publication there are some controversial points, attempts to analyze the family problems of young people, however, mostly they try to avoid these fruitless discourses.

The next group of studies relates to teaching. These publications mainly consider the problem of preparing young people for family relationships from the point of view of including relevant subjects in the school curriculum.

At the end of the 2000s, universities and colleges included the subject "Family Psychology" in accordance with the approved plans of the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education and the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers. Despite the fact that the textbook "Family Psychology" was published specifically for lyceums and colleges, it was not fully implemented. We have studied the current situation in the above-mentioned educational institutions, the curriculum of which still does not include subjects to prepare for family life in any form. Despite this, many scientific studies have been conducted that relate to various family problems, which indicate the need to prepare young people for family life. One important circumstance that we discovered is that among scientific works on the issue of preparing young people for family life there is parallelism with the researches of scientists from other post-soviet countries. This means that some Uzbek authors conducted research in Uzbekistan,

when the topic, methods and conclusions of studies in other post-soviet republics were similar. This demonstrates the similarity of schools, methods and resources of post-soviet academic space.

After making extended analysis of many issues in the framework of this study, we recommend special school subject Family Life Education (FLE) in the high schools of Uzbekistan. Supposedly, this subject will be elaborated based on two programs: Japanese FLE and Belarussian school program called *“Basics of Family Life: Preparation for Marriage and Family Life: 9th grade”* by V.V.Martinova, E.K.Pogodina (Appendix 6)²⁰.

In the process of studying this issue, we were able to conduct several surveys among married young people and their parents about family problems and divorce. For the first time, it was possible to discover that despite the strong moral values and preparedness of young people, the role of third parties in the destruction of young families in the person of the parents of the bride or groom is high.

Based on above mentioned originality of this study can be explained by the following:

1. This study provides evidence for the need for family preparation by addressing the noneducational context.

2. It was found that although the religious

preparation of the family is most favorable for family happiness, this mechanism cannot be applied to the entire society.

3. It was determined that the increase in family divorces does not depend on the economic status of families, but on the lack or poor family life education.

4. The reasons for the lack of training in Preparation for Family Relations in the education system were identified, despite the presence of some ministry-approved subjects.

5. It was found that the studies conducted in Uzbekistan are relevant from the point of view of preserving the institution of the family, although they could not influence the government's decision to introduce effective subjects into the educational system.

6. A comparative analysis was carried out and it was found that the most optimal mechanism for preparing the younger generation for family relationships in Uzbekistan is the family and mahalla, rather than the education system.

7. As a result of the study, it was proposed that the most optimal school program for Preparation for Family Relations in Uzbekistan may be a combination of the Japanese subject “Family Life Education” and the Belarussian subject “Basics of Family Life: Preparation for Marriage and Family Life: 9th grade.”

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²⁰ At the end of this research, preliminary topics of Family Life Education program for Uzbek schools is given, based on above-mentioned Belarussian program. (Appendix 6).

TA'LIM TIZIMIDA YOSHLARNI OILAVIY HAYOTGA TAYYORLASH – DOLZARB MUAMMO

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Annotation. Mazkur maqolada ta'lim tizimida yoshlarni oilaviy hayotga tayyorlash – dolzarb muammo ekanligi, bu o'z navbatida oilalarda sog'lom muhitni tarkib toptirishga hamda shu orqali oila mustahkamligini ta'minlashga zamin yaratishi, bu jarayonni maktabgacha ta'lim, xalq ta'limi va oliy ta'lim tizimida joriy etish bo'yicha zarur chora-tadbirlar amalga oshirilayotganligi, o'tkazilgan ijtimoiy-psixologik tadqiqot natijalari ko'rib chiqilgan.

Tayanch iboralar: oila, yoshlarni oilaga tayyorlash, oila muhiti, sog'lom muhit, oila psixologiyasi, oilaviy munosabatlarga oid tasavvurlar.

Ma'lumki, azaldan sharq mamlakatlari xalqlari ongida oilaning muqaddasligi, er va xotin o'rtasidagi o'zaro hurmat munosabati, farzandning sog'lom tarbiyasidagi oilaning beqiyos roli asrlar davomida shakllanib kelgan. Oilaga nisbatan millatning urf-odat va an'analarini saqlash va davom ettiruvchi dargoh sifatida qaralgan.

Mazkur sohada davlatning vazifalari oilani mustahkamlashdan, oilaviy munosabatlarni o'zaro muhabbat, ishonch va hurmat, hamjihatlik, bir-biriga yordam berish hamda oila oldida uning barcha a'zolarining mas'ulligi hissi asosida qurishdan, oila a'zolari o'z huquqlarini to'sqinliksiz amalga oshirishini hamda bu huquqlarning himoya qilinishini ta'minlashdan iboratdir¹.

Qayd etilgan vazifalarni amalga oshirishda yoshlarni oilaviy hayotga tayyorlash eng dolzarb masalalardan biri hisoblanadi. Yoshlarni oilaviy hayotga tayyorlash faqat shaxsiy, boshqalarga aloqasi yo'qdek ko'rinadi, ammo bu qarash millatimiz ravnaqiga, xalqimiz odobiga, kelajagiga, nasli-nasabiga putur yetkazishdan saqlovchi omildir.

Tarixga nazar soladigan bo'lsak, oilalarda o'g'il bolalarga xos fazilatlar hamiyat, or-nomus tuyg'usi singdirilgan, ota-onaga, yaqinlariga, Vataniga vafodor va fidoiy, g'ayratli, mehnatsevar qilib tarbiyalangan. Qiz bolalarga birinchi o'rinda iffatli va hayoli bo'lish, xushfe'l, odobli, itoatkor, shirinsuhan, sabrli

bo'lishdan saboq berilgan.

Bu borada tarbiya beruvchilarning o'zlari namuna bo'lishgan, yigit va qizlar ijobiy xislatlarni bobobuvilari, ota-onalari va boshqa qarindoshlaridan ko'rib andoza olishgan. Oila boshlig'i - otaga nisbatan hurmat ehtiromni farzandlar onalaridan o'rganishgan. Ota obro'sini o'z o'rnida tutib, ayoli va farzandlari bilan muomalada og'ir vazmin bo'lgan.

Hozirda ba'zi ota-onalarda asosiy muammo o'g'il-qizining ahloq odobi, ilm-ma'naviyati emas, balki ularning moddiy jihatdan ta'minlanganligi deb hisoblashmoqda.

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Sh.M. Mirziyoev 2017-yil 15-iyunda "Ijtimoiy bar-qarorlikni ta'minlash, muqaddas dinimizning sofligini asrash – davr talabi" mavzusidagi anjumanda so'zlagan nutqlarida "Turmush qurgan yoshlar orasida hayotni yengil-yelpi tasavvur qilish, oila muqaddas ekanini tushunib yetmaslik holatlari ham, afsuski, uchrab turibdi. Yosh oilalar orasida arzimmas sabablar bilan ajralishlar ko'payib bormoqda. Begunoh bolalar yetim bo'lib, mehr va e'tiborga eng tashna vaqtda ota-ona tarbiyasidan chetda qolmoqda" deb ta'kidladilar².

Nikohdan ajralishlar asosan 20-35 yosh orasidagi fuqarolar tomonidan amalga oshirilayotganligi o'z navbatida, yoshlar ongida oila va uning muqaddasligi haqidagi tushunchalarning sayozlashib borayotgan-

¹ <http://www.uz24.uz>

² <http://www.president.uz>

ligini ko'rsatmoqda. Shuning uchun ham yoshlarni oila-nikoh munosabatlariga tayyorlash muhim vazifa sifatida o'zini namoyon etadi. Bu borada ta'lim tizimining barcha bo'g'inlarida oilaga oid tushunchalarni yoshlarga o'rgatib borish zarurdir.

Oilalarning mustahkamligi jamiyatning iqtisodiy, ijtimoiy, siyosiy, milliy xavfsizligini, uning ravnaqi, taraqqiyotini belgilovchi hal qiluvchi omil hisoblanadi. Hozirgi vaqtda jamiyatimiz uchun jiddiy xavf tug'dirayotgan iqtisodiy, ijtimoiy, siyosiy, ekologik, ichki va tashqi omillarning tahdidi ortib borayotgan

ayni vaqtda oilalar mustahkamligini ta'minlashning asosiy yo'li bo'lgan yoshlarni oilaviy hayotga tayyorlash masalasi hech kechiktirib bo'lmaydigan, jiddiy yondoshishni talab etuvchi davlat miqyosidagi dolzarb masaladir.

Bugungi kunda yoshlarni nikohga tayyorlash fuqarolik holati dalolatnomalarini yozish bo'limlari qoshida tashkil etilgan "Yosh oila quruvchilar maktabi" va "Oila dorilfununi" mashg'ulotlari doirasida amalga oshirib kelinmoqda. Ushbu mashg'ulotlarda shifokorlar, huquqshunoslar, xotin-qizlar qo'mitalari

xodimlari, O'zbekiston yoshlar ittifoqi vakillari yoshlarga nikohgacha tibbiy ko'rikdan o'tish foydalari, erta turmush va yaqin qarindoshlar o'rtasidagi nikohning og'ir oqibatlari, oila salomatligi mavzularida tushuntirishlar berib kelmoqdalar.

Biroq, FHDYO organlari bevosita nikohni va nikohdan ajralganlikni amalga oshiruvchi va qayd qiluvchi organ bo'lib, bir vaqtning o'zida nikohni va nikohdan ajralganlikni qayd qilish, ajralishlarni oldini olish hamda yoshlarni nikohga tayyorlash bo'yicha "Yosh oila quruvchilar maktabi" va "Oila dorilfununi" ushbu organ qoshida tashkil etilganligi bugungi kunda o'z samarasini bermayotganligini ko'rsatmoqda.

Shu bilan birga, mamlakatimizda yoshlarni nikohga tayyorlash tartibi tizimli ravishda yo'lga qo'yilmaganligi, "Yosh oila quruvchilar maktabi" va "Oila dorilfununi"ning huquqiy asoslari va aniq bir metodikaning mavjud emasligi hisobotlar uchungina

yig'ilishlar, davra suhbatlari tashkil etish amaliyoti yuzuga kelganligini ko'rsatmoqda.

Mutaxassislar mazkur tadbirlarda yoshlar asosan majburiy tarzda ishtirok etishlari, ko'p hollarda auditoriya xuddi majburlab bir joyga to'planganday tuyulishini va tadbirlarning ta'sirchanligi kamligini bildirishmoqda.

Yoshlarni oilaviy hayotga tayyorlash, zamonaviy namunali oilani shakllantirish, uning ma'naviy-axloqiy negizlari va an'anaviy oilaviy qadriyatlarini mustahkamlash bo'yicha maqsadli ishlar olib borilmayotganligi, erta nikohlarning, oilalardagi nizoli holatlar va ajrashishlarning oldini olishda yoshlarni oilaviy hayotga tayyorlash, oiladagi nizoli holatlarni hal qilishning huquqiy va psixologik asoslarini o'rgatish, ajrashishlarning oldini olish, shuningdek, oiladagi ma'naviy-axloqiy qadriyatlarni mustahkamlash muhim vazifadir. Shu bilan birga oiladagi ma'naviy axloqiy qadriyatlarni mustah-

kamlash asosiy vazifalardandir.

Jahon tajribasiga e'tibor qaratsak, ta'lim oluvchilarni oilaviy hayotga tayyorlash maktab dasturlariga kiritilgan. Xususan, Shvetsiyada 1942-yildan, Chexiya va Slovakiyada 1960-yildan buyon "Otalik va onalik tamoyillari", Yaponiyada boshlang'ich ta'limning o'zida "Oilaviy hayotga tayyorlash" kurslari va Polshada 1973-yildan "Oiladagi hayotga moslashish" maxsus kurslari mavjud. Ushbu kurslar yoshlarni oila to'g'risidagi qonunlar, sevgi-muhabbat to'g'risidagi tushunchalar, oilada farzand ko'rish psixologiyasi haqidagi bilimlarga o'rgatadi³.

Bu borada yoshlarni oilaga tayyorlab borishni maktabgacha ta'limda oila haqida turli rolklar, multimedia mahsulotlarini namoyish etish orqali, umumta'lim maktablari yuqori sinf o'quvchilariga "Oila etikasi va psixologiyasi" darsini kiritish, oliy ta'lim tizimida esa "Oila psixologiyasi" kursini o'quv dasturiga kiritish maqsadga muvofiqdir.

Buning uchun obyektiv asos sifatida yoshlarning oilaviy hayot haqidagi tasavvurlarini ilmiy-amaliy jihatdan o'rgandik. Jumladan, umumta'lim maktablaridagi yuqori sinfdagi tahsil olayotgan qizlarning va harbiy tizimdagi askarlar va kursantlarning oilaviy hayotga oid tasavvurlari o'rganildi.

Joriy yilning iyun-iyul oylari davomida O'zbekiston Respublikasi Qurolli Kuchlar Akademiyasi, Chirchiq oliy tank qo'mondonlik muxandislik bilim yurti kursantlari hamda Samarqand, Farg'ona, Andijon viloyatlarida joylashgan muddatli harbiy xizmatni o'tayotgan askarlarda yigitlarni oilaviy hayot haqidagi tasavvur va fikrlari o'rganildi.

Kursant va askarlarni saralashda ularning turli viloyatdan bo'lishi, yoshlari har xil bo'lishi, uylanmagan bo'lishiga e'tibor berildi. Tadqiqot ishida jami 500 nafar yigitlarning oilaviy hayotga tayyorgarlik darajasini aniqlashga qaratilgan "Yigitlarning oilaviy hayot haqidagi tasavvurlari" mavzusida ijtimoiy-psixologik so'rovnoma o'tkazildi, "Siz oilaviy hayotga tayyormisiz?" mavzusidagi aniq savollar hamda oiladagi muammoli vaziyatlar taqdim etildi.

1. Askarlar hamda kursantlarning oilaviy hayot haqidagi tasavvurlari bir-biridan farqlanishi aniqlandi.

2. Kursantlar yetuk shaxs, komil inson va oila muammolarini hal qilishda malakalari askarlarga qaraganda ko'proq ekanligi malum bo'ldi.

3. Kursantlar bilan olib borilgan muhokamadan hamda Akademiyada ta'lim beruvchi o'qituvchilardan so'ralganda ma'lum bo'ldiki, kursantlarda oila masalalari va oilaga tayyorlash bo'yicha "Oila psixologiyasi" kursi davomida ta'lim beriladi. Ularda sabr-toqat, iroda va mas'uliyatni his etish kabi shaxs xususiyatlarini tarkib topishida jismoniy

marshg'ulotlar hamda ta'lim jarayoni bevosita ta'sir qiladi.

4. Askar yigitlar guruhida o'tkazilgan fokus guruhning natijalariga ko'ra yigitlarning oilaviy munosabatlar va oilaning muammolarini hal qilishda deyarli barcha vazifalarni ayollar zimmasiga tashlab qo'yish, onam va xotinim hammasini eplaydi deb qarash mavjudligi aniqlandi hamda muammoli vaziyatlarni yechishda oila bo'yicha bilim va malakalari yetishmasligi malum bo'ldi.

Takliflar:

1. Yigitlarni oilaviy hayotga tayyorlashning sifatini oshirishda harbiylashgan oliy ta'lim tizimidagi kursantlar o'quv rejasiga "Oila psixologiyasi" o'quv kursi soatlarini ko'paytirishni amalga oshirish zarur.

2. Muddatli harbiy xizmatdagi askarlarda o'tkaziladigan ma'naviyat soatlarini muntazamligini ta'minlash va ko'paytirish, xususan, oila va oilaviy munosabatlarga bag'ishlangan targ'ibot ta'sirchanligini oshirish zarur.

3. Harbiylashgan oliy ta'lim tizimi hamda muddatli harbiy xizmatdagi oila qurish arafasidagi yigitlarda oila bilan bog'liq qadriyatlarini psixologik treninglar orqali mustahkamlanishiga e'tibor qaratish lozim.

Shu tarzda umumta'lim maktablarining yuqori sinf o'quvchi qizlarining oilaviy hayot haqidagi tasavvurlari ilmiy tadqiq etildi. Tadqiqot ishida jami 1400 nafar qizlarning oilaviy hayotga tayyorgarlik darajasini aniqlashga qaratilgan "Yoshlarning oilaviy hayot haqidagi tasavvurlari" mavzusida ijtimoiy-psixologik so'rovnoma o'tkazildi, "Siz oilaviy hayotga tayyormisiz?" mavzusidagi aniq savollar hamda

³ <http://makarenko-useum.ru> "Материалы 8-х международных Макаренковских студенческих педагогических чтений" Екатеринбург, 7 апреля 2011 г

oiladagi muammoli vaziyatlar taqdim etildi.

Ayrim natijalardan ko'rinadiki, oila qurishda qizlarning ham oilaga tayyorlik darajalari keskin tafovutlanadi.

1-jadval

“Siz o‘zingizni oila qurgandan so‘ng onalik mas‘uliyatiga tayyor deb hisoblaysizmi?” savoliga qizlar javobi natijalari

Siz o‘zingizni oila qurgandan so‘ng onalik mas‘uliyatiga tayyor deb hisoblaysizmi?		
	Javoblar	%
A.	Ha, tayyor deb hisoblayman	14
V.	Biroz tayyor deb hisoblayman	20
S.	Tayyor deb hisoblamayman	23
D.	Bu borada bilimlarim kam deb hisoblayman	43
	Jami	100%

2-jadval.

“Siz o‘zingizni oila qurgandan so‘ng onalik mas‘uliyatiga tayyor deb hisoblaysizmi?” savoli qizlar javobi natijalari

Siz o‘zingizni ayol rolini bajarishga to‘laqonli tayyor deb hisoblaysizmi?		
	Javoblar	%
A.	Tayyor deb hisoblayman	12
V.	Biroz tayyor deb hisoblayman	25
S.	Tayyor deb hisoblamayman	33
D.	Bu borada bilimlarim kam deb hisoblayman	30
	Jami	100%

Yuqoridagilardan kelib chiqib, bugungi kunda yoshlarni nikohga tayyorlash sohasida quyidagi muammolar mavjudligini qayd etish mumkin:

Birinchidan, yoshlarni nikohga tayyorlashning ta'lim bilan bog'liq tizimi mavjud emas.

Ikkinchidan, yoshlarni nikohga tayyorlash jarayoni tizimli ravishda yo'lga qo'yilmagan hamda yoshlarni oilaviy hayotga tayyorlashning aniq metodikasi ishlab chiqilmagan. Yoshlar asosan majburiy tarzda ishtirok etishlari, aksariyat hollarda auditoriya xuddi majburlab bir joyga to'planganday tuyulishi va tadbirlarning ta'sirchanligi kamligini bildirishmoqda.

Uchinchidan, ma'lumotlarni yoshlarga yetkazish usuli va shakllari bugungi kun talablariga javob bermaydi, bu borada axborot texnologiyalarining so'ngi imkoniyatlaridan foydalanish talab darajasida emas. Mutaxassislar yoshlarni fikr va mulohazalarini eshitmayotganligini ta'kidlashmoqda.

Jamiyatning asosiy bo'g'ini hisoblangan oilalar ajrimining oldini olishda yoshlarni oilaviy hayotga to'g'ri tayyorlash muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Bu o'z navbatida jamiyat milliy qadriyatlarining asrab avaylanishiga xizmat qilib, kelajak yoshlarning to'liqsiz oilalarda tarbiyalanishi va oqibatida yuzaga kelishi mumkin bo'lgan salbiy holatlarning oldini olishga xizmat qiladi.

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Аннотация: В статье рассматриваются вопросы подготовки молодежи к семье как актуальной темы современности в сфере образования, с помощью которой обеспечивается стабильность и прочность семьи. Обоснована необходимость введения этого процесса в систему образования: в дошкольное, в среднее и высшее образование, приведены результаты проведенного социально-психологического исследования.

Ключевые слова: семья, подготовка молодёжи к семье, климат семьи, здоровая среда семьи, психология семьи, представления о семье и семейных отношений.

Annotatsiya: The article deals with the issues of preparing youth for the family as an actual topic of the present in the sphere of education, with the help of which the stability and strength of the family are ensured. The necessity of introducing this process into the education system is justified: in preschool, in secondary and higher education, the results of the conducted social and psychological research are given.

Kalit so'zlar: family, preparation of youth for family, family climate, healthy family environment, family psychology, family and family relations.

JAMIYAT TRANSFORMATSIYASI SHAROITIDA YOSHLAR BANDLIGI OMILINING IJTIMOY XAVFSIZLIKKA TA'SIRI

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Annotation. Maqolada jamiyatdagi transformatsion jarayonlar sharoitida ijtimoiy xavfsizlik holatini baholashga oid yondashuvlar va yoshlar bandligini ta'minlashning ijtimoiy xavfsizlikka ta'siri ilmiy yoritilgan. Shuningdek, ijtimoiy xavfsizlikning istiqboldagi holatiga ta'sir qiluvchi omillar yuzasidan tahlillar amalga oshirilgan.

Tayanch iboralar: Transformatsiya, tendensiya, benchmarking, mehnat bozori balansi, sotsiologik, ijtimoiy xavfsizlik

Transformatsion jarayonlar kuchayib borgan sari hozirgi sharoitda milliy xavfsizlik kesimida ularni tahlil qilish, yuzaga keladigan imkoniyatlar va tahdidlarni baholash zaruriyati paydo bo'lmoqda. Qolaversa, mana shunday sharoitda O'zbekiston ijtimoiy davlat deb e'lon qilinishi istiqbolda kutilayotgan global muammolarni hisobga olgan holda ijtimoiy siyosatni takomillashtirib borishni taqozo etadi. Bu holat iqtisodiy xavfsizlikni ta'minlashda innovatsion yondashuvni hisobga olishni nazarda tutsa, demografik xavfsizlikni ta'minlashda inson kapitali ya'ni, insonning eng asosiy resursga aylanayotganligini, axborot xavfsizligini ta'minlashda virtuallashuv va raqamlashish darajasining ortishini, mintaqaviy xavfsizlikni ta'minlashda davlatlararo integratsiyalarning kuchayishi va chegaralarning birlashishini, mintaqaviy xavfsizlikni ta'minlashda esa dunyoviy tartibotning o'zgarishini inobatga olishni nazarda tutadi. Bu haqida O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti "Jahondagi shiddatli raqobat sharoitida yetuk mutaxassislar tayyorlash, o'zgaruvchan mehnat bozori talablariga moslashishni bugun hayotning o'zi taqozo etmoqda"¹ degan fikrlarni bildirib o'tgan.

Dastlab global transformatsiya tushunchasiga ta'rif beradigan bo'lsak, bunda transformatsiya global darajada sodir bo'ladigan va jamiyat hayotining turli sohalariga, jumladan, iqtisodiyot,

siyosat, ijtimoiy munosabatlar, texnologiya va atrof-muhitga ta'sir qiluvchi o'zgarishlar jarayoni nazarda tutiladi. Bu tendensiya nafaqat alohida mamlakatlar yoki mintaqalarda, balki xalqaro miqyosda ham o'zgarishlar ro'y berayotganidan dalolat beradi. Global o'zgarishlarga texnologik innovatsiyalar, globallashuv, iqlim o'zgarishi, demografik o'zgarishlar va geosiyosiy siljishlar kabi turli omillar sabab bo'lishi mumkin. Transformatsion jarayonlarning o'ziga xosligi shundaki, u jamiyat uchun yangi muammolar va imkoniyatlarni keltirib chiqarishi mumkin.

Global transformatsiyaning asosiy o'ziga xosliklarini yana xalqaro savdo va investitsiyalar hajmining oshishida, raqamli iqtisodiyotning rivojlantirishida, migratsiya va madaniyatlararo o'zaro ta'sirning kuchayishida, jamiyatdagi ustuvorliklar va qadriyatlarining o'zgarishida, fuqarolik jamiyatining qarorlar qabul qilishdagi rolining faollashishida kuzatiladi.

Jamiyatdagi transformatsion jarayonlar o'z navbatida ijobiy va salbiy oqibatlariga olib keladi. Bir tomonidan bunday jarayonlar iqtisodiy o'sishga, innovatsiyalarga va turmush sharoitlarini yaxshilashga yordam bersa, ikkinchi tomondan tengsizlik, ekologik muammolar va ijtimoiy ziddiyatlarni keltirib chiqarishi mumkin.

Jahondagi global tendensiyalar 2050-yilga borib

¹ O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Ш.М. Мирзиёевнинг 2023 йил 13 февраль кунги Ижтимоий соҳаларга масъул раҳбарларни қабул қилишидаги нутқи // <https://president.uz/uz/lists/view/5816>. Мурожаат санаси: 2023 йил 24 ноябрь.

dunyo aholisi 9,7 mlrd ga yetib, bunda 65 yoshdan oshganlar ulushi 2 barobarga ko'payadi², ya'ni har 6 ta aholidan biri keksa yoshdagi aholiga to'g'ri keladi. Shu bilan birga, 2050- yilga kelib energiyaga bo'lgan talab ham o'z o'rnida 2 barobar, suvga bo'lgan talab 30 foizga ortadi. Natijada suv tanqisligi tufayli 45 foiz global YaIM, 35 foiz ish o'rinlarining qisqarish xavfi mavjud³.

Bundan tashqari, global suv tanqisligining o'sish fonida bir tomondan oziq-ovqat mahsulotlarini yetishtirish 40 foizga kamaysa, ikkinchi tomondan oziq-ovqatga bo'lgan yalpi talab 50 foizga, hayvonlar oziq-ovqatiga bo'lgan talab 70 foizga⁴ ortadi. Bu, o'z o'rinida, oziq-ovqatlarni yaratish va iste'mol talabi o'rtasidagi salbiy farq 56 foizgacha yetishi kutilmoqda.

Shu bilan birga, 2030-yilga qadar iqlim o'zgarishlari tufayli 100 mln aholi kambag'allikka duchor bo'lishi, qolaversa, oziq-ovqat yetishmovchiligi va raqamlashish natijasida ish o'rinlarining qisqarishi ortidan kambag'allik ko'rsatkichlarining ortishi prog-noz qilinmoqda. Xususan, 2050-yilga borib global raqamlashish ko'rsatkichlari 50 foizga ortib, natijada ish o'rinlari 35 foizga qisqarish dinamikasi kutilmoqda⁵. O'z navbatida istiqbolda qayta tiklanuvchi energiyadan foydalanish ko'rsatkichlarining ortishi, ushbu tizimning rivojlanishi tufayli har yili 12 mln, 2050-yilga qadar esa 145 mln "yashil" ish o'rinlari yaratilishi rejalashtirilmoqda.

Global transformatsion jarayonlarning bunday o'zgarishi mehnat resurslarining mobillik ko'rsatkichining o'sishiga olib keladi. Xususan, 2050-yilga kelib mehnat resurslarining mobillik ko'rsatkichi 3 barobar ortib, ularning o'rtacha yoshi 40 yoshdan oshishi kutilmoqda. Jamiyatda ijtimoiy sohalari-ning bunday transformatsiyasi IT sohasining barqaror rivojlanib borishiga ham ta'sir ko'rsatadi. Jumladan, xalqaro tashkilotlar tomonidan olib borilgan tadqiqotlarga ko'ra, 2030-yilga kelib IT sohasida har yili 11 trln AQSh dollari miqdorida daromad olinadi.

Bu tendensiyalar o'z navbatida yoshlar bandligini ta'minlash tizimiga ham ta'sir ko'rsatadi. Dastlab ushbu yo'nalishdagi istiqbolda erishish ko'zda tutilgan strategik maqsadlarimizni ko'rib chiqsak, 2030-yilga qadar 1 mln yoshlar bandligini ta'minlash orqali yoshlar ishsizligini 6 foizga tushirish ko'zda tutilgan bo'lsa, mehnat unumdorligi va nogironlar bandligini 2 barobarga oshirish hamda ishsizlikni

6,5 foizga tushirish rejalashtirilgan .

Umuman olganda, global transformatsiya zamonaviy dunyoning ajralmas qismi bo'lib, milliy xavfsizlikni ta'minlashda sodir bo'layotgan zamonaviy tendensiyalarga nisbatan davlatlar, tashkilotlar va shaxslar tomonidan e'tibor va moslashishni talab qiladi.

Transformatsion sharoitda ijtimoiy xavfsizlik holatini baholash murakkab bo'lib, u ko'p omillarni o'z ichiga oladi va kontekstga qarab farq qilishi mumkin. Biroq, ushbu sharoitda ijtimoiy xavfsizlikni baholash uchun ishlatilishi mumkin bo'lgan quyidagi umumiy metodlar mavjud:

statistik ma'lumotlarni to'plash. Bu o'z navbatida, ijtimoiy so'rovlar, suhbatlar o'tkazish va statistik ma'lumotlarni tahlil qilish orqali amalga oshirilib, jamiyatdagi jinoyat, zo'ravonlik yoki ishsizlik kabi ijtimoiy xavfsizlikning ayrim jihatlarini o'lchashga yordam beradi;

xavfsizlik indekslari: Global tinchlik indeksi, jinoyat indeksi kabi xavfsizlik indekslaridan foydalanish turli mintaqalar yoki mamlakatdagi xavfsizlik darajasini solishtirish imkonini beradi. Bu orqali ijtimoiy xavfsizlik holatiga xalqaro darajada baho berish mumkin;

iqtisodiy barqarorlik tahlili. Iqtisodiy barqarorlik ijtimoiy xavfsizlikni ta'minlashga xizmat qiluvchi muhim omildir. Mamlakatning yalpi ichki mahsuloti, jon boshiga aholi daromadlari, kambag'allik darajasi, daromadlar tengsizligi holati va bandlik darajasi, o'rtacha ish haqqi, tirikchilik minimumi kabi ko'rsatkichlarni o'rganish ijtimoiy xavfsizlik holatini baholashga yordam beradi:

ijtimoiy fikr tahlili. Sotsiologik so'rovlar o'tkazish fuqarolarning hukumat, huquqni muhofaza qiluvchi organlar va ijtimoiy institutlarga ishonch darajasini aniqlash orqali ham ijtimoiy xavfsizlik holatini, tahdidlarning darajasini baholash mumkin. Shu bilan birga, sotsiologik so'rovlar jamiyatdagi xavfsizlik hissi haqida tushuncha beradi. Sotsiologik tadqiqotlar ijtimoiy xavfsizlikni ta'minlanganlik holati bo'yicha subyektiv bahoni beradi va bu obyektiv baholash usullari orqali olingan ma'lumotlar bilan qiyosiy tahlil qilish imkonini beradi;

hayot sifatini tahlili. Ta'lim, sog'liqni saqlash, uy-joy, ijtimoiy himoya, ijtimoiy ta'minot va hayotdan qoniqish kabi omillarni o'rganish va ularning qiyosiy tahlili ijtimoiy xavfsizlik darajasini baholashga yordam beradi;

² Кенечи Окелеке, Саяли Бороле. Преодоление цифрового разрыва в Центральной Азии и на Южном Кавказе. GSMA Intelligence 2023 г. – С. 38.

³ John Armit, Sadie Morgan. Thames Estuary 2050 Growth Commission 2050 Vision. England 2019. – P 36.

⁴ Approaches to Measuring Social Exclusion. Prepared by the UNECE Task Force on the Measurement of Social Exclusion. United Nations 2022. – P. 76/

⁵ Цифровая трансформация отраслей: стартовые условия и приоритеты: докл. к XXII Апр. междунар. науч. конф. по проблемам развития экономики и общества, Москва, 13-30 апр. 2021 г. / Г. И. Абдрахманова, К. Б. Быховский, Н. Н. Веселитская, К. О. Вишнеvский, Л. М. Гохберг и др. ; рук. авт. кол. П. Б. Рудник ; науч. ред. Л. М. Гохберг, П. Б. Рудник, К. О. Вишнеvский, Т. С. Зинина ; Нац. исслед. ун-т «Высшая школа экономики». – М.: Изд. дом Высшей школы экономики, 2021. – 239 с.

sifatiy tadqiqotlar. Chuqurlashtirilgan intervyular va fokus-guruhlar kabi sifatiy tadqiqot usullari orqali ijtimoiy xavfsizlikning o'ziga xos jihatlarini o'rganish va odamlarning fikri, xohish-istagini va tajribasini tushunish mumkin. Masalan, tadqiqotchilar ijtimoiy xavfsizlikka qanday omillar ta'sir ko'rsatishi va vaziyatni yaxshilash uchun qanday choralar ko'rish mumkinligini chuqurroq tahlil qilish uchun o'rganilayotgan muammoning tashuvchilari bilan suhbatlar o'tkazish mumkin;

benchmarking: Benchmarking usuli ijtimoiy xavfsizlik holatini baholashda ishlatiladigan usullardan biri bo'lib, u orqali hududlar yoki davlatga oid ma'lumotlar sohalar kesimida samaradorlik nuqtai-nazaridan taqqoslanadi va tahlil qilinadi. Bu o'z navbatida, hududlar o'rtasiga ijtimoiy xavfsizlik holati bilan bog'liq farqlarni aniqlash va boshqa

joylarda yuzaga kelishi mumkin bo'lgan risklarni barvaqt aniqlash imkonini beradi.

Yoshlar bandligini ta'minlashni ijtimoiy xavfsizlik nuqtai-nazaridan baholash uchun mehnat bozorining joriy holatini ko'rib chiqadigan bo'lsak, mehnat bozorining asosini mehnat resurslari, ishlab chiqarish vositalari, ijtimoiy foydali bo'lgan mahsulot ishlab chiqarish yoki xizmat ko'rsatishga oid munosabatlar tashkil qilsa, mamlakatimizda mehnat resurslari 20,3 mln ni, iqtisodiy nafaol aholi 4,4 mln, iqtisodiy faol aholi qariyb 16 mln ni tashkil qiladi. Shundan iqtisodiyotda bandlar 14,2 mln ni, tashkil qilib, ularning 43 foizdan ortig'i rasmiy sektorda, 42 foiz norasmiy sektorda, 14 foizi esa tashqi migratsiyada mehnat qiladi, ishga joylashishga muhtoj shaxslar 1,8 mln ni tashkil qiladi (1-rasm).

1-rasm. Mehnat bozorining balansi⁶

Mehnat bozorining balansi asosida sohadagi joriy holatni ijtimoiy xavfsizlik kesimida baholashda obyektiv, subyektiv, va integral yondashuvlardan foydalanildi. Obyektiv baholashda statistik ko'rsatkichlar orqali indikatorlarning joriy holati ochib berildi. (1-jadval).

3.1-jadval

O'zbekistonda yoshlar bandligini ta'minlashdagi ijtimoiy xavfsizlik holatini ob'ektiv baholash (1-guruh indikatorlari)⁷

No	Indikator nomi	O'lchov birligi	Chegaraviy qiymat	Amalda*	Sharoit yaratuvchi omil
1.	Aholining o'rtacha yillik o'sish sur'ati	foiz	1,3	2,1	demografik
2.	Umumiy aholi sonida mehnat yoshidan kichik shaxslar ulushi	foiz	22,0	31,4	demografik

⁶ Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президенти ҳузуридаги Давлат статистика агентлиги маълумотлари асосида муаллиф томонидан тайёрланган.

⁷ Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президенти ҳузуридаги Давлат статистика агентлиги маълумотлари асосида муаллиф томонидан тайёрланган.

3.	Umumiy aholi sonida mehnatga layoqatli yoshdagi shaxslar ulushi	foiz	58,0	59,8	demografik
4.	Aholining keksayish koeffitsienti	‰	6,0	4,9	demografik
5.	Mehnatga layoqatli har 100 nafar aholiga to'g'ri keladigan mehnatga layoqatli yoshdan kichik shaxslar	soni	40,0	52	demografik
6.	Mehnatga layoqatli har 100 nafar aholiga to'g'ri keladigan mehnatga layoqatli yoshdan katta shaxslar	soni	30,0	23	demografik
7.	Mehnatga layoqatli har 100 nafar aholiga to'g'ri keladigan mehnatga layoqatsiz shaxslar soni	foiz	70,0	67	demografik, sog'liqni saqlash,
8.	Tug'ilishning umumiy koeffitsienti	‰	20,0	26	demografik
9.	O'limning umumiy koeffitsienti	‰	10,0	5,1	sog'liqni saqlash
10.	Chaqaloqlar o'limi	‰	5,0	9,3	sog'liqni saqlash
12	Inqiroz oldi – 2	Inqiroz oldi – 3	Inqiroz – 1	Inqiroz – 2	Inqiroz – 3

Birinchi guruh indikatorlarida demografik omilining o'zni yuqori bo'lib ushbu omilning ijobiy ta'siri tufayli vaziyat nisbatan barqaror. Ikkinchi guruh indikatorlarida boshqa omillarning ta'siri ustuvor bo'lganligi sababli inqiroz oldi va inqiroz

ko'rsatkichlari mavjud. Xususan, mehnat bozorining keskinlik darajasi me'yordan 2 barobar yuqori, ya'ni talab va taklif munosabatlari disbalans holatda, tashqi migratsiyada norasmiy migratsiyaning ustuvorligi inqiroz holatlarini ko'rsatmoqda (2-jadval).

3.2-jadval

O'zbekistonda yoshlar bandligini ta'minlashdagi ijtimoiy xavfsizlik holatini ob'ektiv baholash (2-guruh indikatorlari)⁸

№	Indikator nomi	O'lchov birligi	Chegaraviy qiymat	Amalda*	Sharoit yaratuvchi omil
1	Mehnat resurslari ulushi	foiz	60	55	Demografik

⁸ Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президенти ҳузуридаги Давлат статистика агентлиги маълумотлари асосида муаллиф томонидан тайёрланган.

2	Iqtisodiy faol aholi ulushi	foiz	50,0	74,4	Demografik
3	Aholi bandligi darajasi	foiz	46,0	62,4	Ish o'rinlari
4	Ishsizlik darajasi	foiz	8,0	11,3	Ish o'rinlari, demografik
5	Mehnat bozorining keskinlik darajasi	birlik	6,0	12,1	Demografik
6	Norasmiy migratsiya ulushi	foiz	1,0	94	Bandlik darajasi
7	Zararli va xavfli mehnat sharoitida bandlar ulushi	foiz	2,0	6,7	Ish o'rinlari
8	Ishlab chiqarishda shikastlanganlik darajasi, 1000 ishlovchiga	‰	0,5	2,6	Mehnat sharoitlari
9	Migratsion o'sish koeffitsienti	‰	0	7,1	Ish o'rinlari
10	Mehnatga layoqatli yoshdagi aholining o'lim koeffitsienti	‰	2,0	4,1	Mehnat sharoitlari
*Inqiroz oldi – 1		Inqiroz oldi – 2	Inqiroz oldi – 3	Inqiroz – 1	Inqiroz – 2
				Inqiroz – 3	

Ijtimoiy xavfsizlik holatini subyektiv baholashda sotsiologik tadqiqot natijalariga tayanilib, bunda asosiy urg'u mehnat resurslarining mehnat sharoitlari va bandlik tizimidan qoniqish darajasiga qaratildi (3.3-jadval). Ushbu yondashuvda mutaxassisligi

va joriy mehnat faoliyatining nomutanosibli, ya'ni so'rovda ishtirok etgan respondentlarning 68 foiz qismi mutaxassisligi bo'yicha ishlamayotganligini, 60 foiz respondentlar ishga joylashishda sun'iy to'siqlarga uchraganini ta'kidlashgan.

3-jadval

O'zbekistonda yoshlar bandligini ta'minlashdagi ijtimoiy xavfsizlik holatini subyektiv baholash⁹

No	Indikator nomi	O'lchov birligi	Chegaraviy qiymat	Amalda*	Sharoit yaratuvchi omil
1	Mehnat sharoitlaridan umumiy qoniqish darajasi	foiz	60+	53	Mehnat sharoitlari
2	Yoshlar bandligini ta'minlashga oid davlat siyosatidan qoniqish darajasi	foiz	65+	51	Tashkiliy
3	Ish o'rinlaridan qoniqish darajasi	foiz	70+	38	Tashkiliy

⁹ Социологик тадқиқот натижалари асосида муаллиф томонидан тайёрланган.

4	Mutaxassisligi doirasida egallagan bilimlaridan qoniqish darajasi	foiz	80+	60	Tashkiliy		
5	Joriy mehnat faoliyati va mutaxassisligining mutanosiblik darajasi	foiz	66+	32	Mehnat bozori		
6	Ishga joylashishda sun'iy qiyinchiliklar (to'siqlar) ga duch kelish darajasi	foiz	30-	60	Tashkiliy		
7	Mehnat faoliyati va maoshidan qoniqish darajasi	foiz	70+	59	Ta'lim, tashkiliy		
8	Mehnat sharoitlari va bandlik tizimidan qoniqishning umumiy indeksi	foiz	75+	63	Tashkiliy		
*Inqiroz oldi – 1		Inqiroz oldi – 2		Inqiroz oldi – 3	Inqiroz – 1	Inqiroz – 2	Inqiroz – 3

Yuqoridagi indikatorlarni tahlili asosida integral baholasak norasmiy mehnat migratsiyasi, norasmiy bandlik, potensial ishsizlikka oid ko'rsatkichlarda vaziyat nisbatan noabarqaror ekanligini ko'rish mumkin

(2-rasm). Yuqoridagi tahlillar asosida yoshlar bandligini ta'minlashdagi ijtimoiy xavfsizlik holati bilan bog'liq salbiy tendensiyalar ham mavjudligini aytish mumkin.

2-rasm. O'zbekistonda yoshlar bandligini ta'minlashdagi ijtimoiy xavfsizlik holatini integral baholash¹⁰

Albatta, bu holatni yumshatish uchun davlat tomonidan choralar ko'rilmoqda. Xususan, ishsiz fuqarolarga jamoat ishlariga jalb qilinganligi uchun haq to'lash, subsidiyalarni berish, bepul kasbga o'qitish, ishsizlik nafaqasini to'lash mexanizmlari, ish beruvchilarga jamoat ishlarini tashkil qilganligi

uchun hamda ishga qabul qilingan xodimni malakasini oshirish uchun sarflangan xarajatlarni to'lab berish, kvotadan ortiq ijtimoiy himoyaga muhtoj shaxsni ishga qabul qilgan har bir xodim uchun 2 baravari miqdorida subsidiyalash, "Ustozshogird" tizimi orqali hunarmandchilikka o'rgatish

¹⁰ Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президенти ҳузуридаги давлат статистика агентлиги, Ўзбекистон Республикаси Камбағалликни қисқартириш ва бандлик вазирлиги маълумотлари ҳамда социологик тадқиқот натижалари асосида муаллиф томонидан тайёрланган.

xarajatlari qoplab berilishining mexanizmlari yo'lga qo'yilgan. Va bandlikka ko'maklashish uchun 2023-yilda 14 trln so'm ajratilgan. Bu ishga joylashishga muhtoj aholi jon boshiga o'rtacha 8,5 mln so'mni tashkil qiladi.

Mamlakatimizda mehnat bozorining istiqboldagi o'zgarish dinamikasiga oid xalqaro tashkilotlar tomonidan olib borilgan tadqiqotlar 2050-yilga borib O'zbekistonda mehnat bozorida yuqori malaka talab qiladigan ishlar ulushi qariyb 2 barobarga o'sishini ko'rsatmoqda. O'z navbatida, nisbatan kam malaka

talab qiladigan ishlar ulushi ham mos ravishda qisqaradi (3-rasm).

Bugungi kunda mehnat bozoriga kirib kelayotgan yoshlarning 50 foizida malakasizlik muammosi mavjudligini inobatga olsak, kelgusida ham bu muammo dolzarb bo'lib qolaveradi. Shu sababli yoshlar bandligini ta'minlashga oid davlat siyosatida maktabning yuqori sinf o'quvchilarini kasb-hunarga o'rgatish, ishsizlarni o'qitish, turli soha xodimlarini malakasini oshirish masalalariga urg'u berilmoqda.

- Yuqori malaka va intellekt talab qiladigan ishlar ulushi
- Nisbatan kam malaka talab qiladigan ishlar ulushi

3-rasm. Mehnat bozorining istiqboldagi o'zgarish dinamikasi

Mamlakatimizda mehnat bozoriga ta'sir ko'rsatuvchi, dividend beruvchi demografik omilning o'zgarish dinamikasi 4-rasmda berilgan bo'lib,

2050 yilga kelib mamlakatimiz aholisi 50,8 mln kishiga yetishi, shu bilan birga, tug'ilish ko'rsatkichi kamayib barqarorlashishi kutilmoqda.

4-rasm. Demografik omilning istiqboldagi o'zgarish dinamikasi: axoli soni (mln. kishi) va o'sish sur'atlari¹¹(%)

Bundan tashqari, nafaqa yoshidagi aholi soni yoshidagi aholiga to'g'ri keladi (5-rasm). Shu bilan birga, migratsion harakatlar 2 barobar ortishi qariyb 2 barobarga ko'payadi ya'ni, 2050-yilda 50 mln aholining 10 mln ga yaqin qismi nafaqa

5-rasm. Demografik omilning istiqboldagi o'zgarish dinamikasi: axoli soni (mln. kishi) va o'sish sur'atlari¹²(%)

O'z navbatida, transformatsion jarayonlar xalqaro darajada ishsizlikka ta'sir ko'rsatadi. Xususan, potensial ishsizlikning global darajasi 2050-yilga borib 24 foizga yetishi prognoz qilinmoqda. Bunga ta'sir qiluvchi omillar 0 dan 10 gacha mezonda baholanganda, ishlab chiqarishning robotlashishi va raqamlashish, texnologik taraqqiyot, sun'iy ong, nanotexnologiya va sintetik biologiya kabi omillarning ta'siri yuqori ekanligini ko'rish mumkin (6-rasm). O'z navbatida, xalqaro mehnat bozorida ushbu yo'nalishdagi mutaxassislarga bo'lgan talab ortib ketadi.

Global ishsizlik bilan bog'liq bu tendensiyalar biz yuqorida ta'kidlagan mamlakatimizdagi ishsizlik darajasini 6,5 foizga tushirish maqsadini amalga oshirishni murakkablashtiradi va kelgusidagi ijtimoiy xavfsizlik holati barqaror bo'lishi uchun hozir zarur chora-tadbirlarni ko'rishga undaydi.

Tahlil natijalari global tendensiyalarning salbiy ta'sirini yumshatish hamda barqaror ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy rivojlanishni saqlab qolishda mehnat unumdorligi muhim ahamiyat kasb etishini ko'rsatmoqda. Ya'ni, jon boshiga real yalpi ichki mahsulotni 1,9 foizga

oshirish uchun mehnat unumdorligini kamida 1,8 foizga oshirish lozim bo'ladi.

Mehnat unumdorligiga ta'sir ko'rsatuvchi asosiy omillardan biri inson kapitali bo'lib, u ma'lum darajada mehnat resurslarining ma'lumot darajasi bilan bog'liq. Shu o'rinda to'xtalib o'tadigan bo'lsak, mamlakatimizda mehnat resurslarining 14,8 foiz oliy ma'lumotli bo'lsa, 56,1 foiz o'rta-maxsus, 29,1 foizi o'rta ma'lumotli. Shu sababli hukumat tomonidan oliy ta'lim bilan qamrov darajasini 50 foizga yetkazish strategik maqsad sifatida belgilanib, tegishli chora-tadbirlar amalga oshirilmoqda.

Umuman olganda ijtimoiy havfsizlik holati murakkab va subyektiv tushuncha bo'lib, uni o'lchash munozaralarga va turli yondashuvlarga sabab bo'lishi mumkin. Qolaversa, jamiyatdagi mavjud transformatsion jarayonlar sharoitida ijtimoiy xavfsizlikning istiqboldagi holatini tahlil qilishning u yoki bu usulini qo'llash vaziyatni obyektiv baholashning to'liq imkonini bermaydi. Shu sababli ijtimoiy xavfsizlik holatini baholashda kompleks yondashuv, ya'ni bir qancha usullarni uzviylikda qo'llash ilmiy tadqiqotning ishonchliligini oshiradi.

¹¹ Прага Карлов Университетининг Ўзбекистондаги демографик vaziyat tўғрисидаги прогнози asosida тайёрланди.

¹² Прага Карлов Университетининг Ўзбекистондаги демографик vaziyat tўғрисидаги прогнози asosida тайёрланди.

6-rasm. Potensial ishsizlikning global darajasiga ta'sir ko'rsatuvchi omillar¹³(%)

Yuqoridagilardan kelib chiqqan holda quyidagi taklif va tavsiyalarni ilgari surish mumkin:

global tendensiyalar asosida mehnat bozorining keskinlik darajasini kamaytirish uchun istiqbolda talab yuqori bo'lgan kasblar: raqamlashtirish, "big data", yashil energetika, robotlashtirish, texnologiyaga xizmat ko'rsatish va boshqa ustuvor kasblarga talabni shakllantirishda davlat axborot siyosati orqali ko'maklashish maqsadga muvofiq;

qishloq xo'jaligini texnologik jihatdan subsidiyalash. Bu orqali bir tomondan nisbatan kam malakali yoshlar ish bilan ta'minlansa ikkinchi tomondan istiqboldagi oziq-ovqat xavfsizligi bilan bog'liq risklarni oldini olish mumkin;

norasmiy bandlikni qisqartirishda hozirgi kunda

o'z-o'zini band qilish va ro'yxatdan o'tmagan tadbirkorlik subyektlarini ro'yxatga olishga ustuvor ahamiyat berilmoqda. Galdagi vazifa esa ro'yxatdan o'tgan tadbirkorlik subyektlarida norasmiy mehnat qilayotgan ishchilarni rasmiylashtirish choralarini ko'rish;

milliy malaka tizimini xalqaro mezonlar asosida qayta ishlash mehnat unumdorligini va inson kapitalini oshirishga ijobiy ta'sir ko'rsatadi. Bu orqali yagona yondashuv asosida kvalifikatsion standartlarni xodimda shakllanganlik darajasini baholash mumkin;

inson kapitalini oshirishda texnologik rivojlanishni qo'llab-quvvatlashga urg'u berish.

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¹³ "Bertelsmann Stiftung" tashkilotining global mehnat bozoriga oid tadqiqot natijalari asosida muallif tomonidan tayyorlandi.

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Аннотация: В статье научно освещены подходы к оценке состояния социальной безопасности в контексте трансформационных процессов в обществе и ее влияние на социальную безопасность, как пример обеспечения занятости молодежи. Также проанализированы факторы, влияющие на будущее состояние социального обеспечения

Ключевые слова: трансформация, тренд, бенчмаркинг, баланс рынка труда, социология, социальные отношения.

Annotatsiya: In the article, the approaches to the evaluation of the state of social security in the context of transformation processes in the society and its impact on social security, as an example of ensuring employment of the youth, were scientifically covered. Also, factors affecting the future state of social security were analyzed

Kalit so'zlar: Transformation, trend, benchmarking, labor market balance, sociological, social relations

CAREER GUIDANCE FOR THE YOUTH OF NEW UZBEKISTAN: Systematic support for young people interested in modern professions

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Abstract. *This article examines the challenges of career guidance and improvement for youth in Uzbekistan. Considering the rapid economic development and the changing needs of the labor market, the importance of guiding young people towards relevant professions is becoming increasingly significant. The study includes an analysis of existing vocational education programs, as well as methods and approaches used to raise awareness among youth about career opportunities. Special attention is paid to the role of government bodies, educational institutions, and business entities in the process of career guidance. In conclusion, recommendations are provided to enhance the system of professional counseling and assistance for young people in choosing a profession, which will serve to more effectively utilize the human resource potential of our country.*

Keywords: *youth, education, employment, youth initiatives, social activism, labor system, professional competence.*

In the new Uzbekistan, young people face numerous challenges and opportunities when choosing their career paths. Given the rapid development of technology and the changing structure of the labor market, it is particularly crucial to guide youth towards modern professions that require new skills and knowledge. An important aspect of this process is the systematic support of young people interested in acquiring education and vocational training that meet the demands of our time.

Public and private organizations, educational institutions, and professional associations play a vital role in creating a favourable environment for youth development. They should not only inform young people about new trends and prospects in various fields but also provide practical opportunities to gain experience through internships, courses, and training programs.

In modern society, young people play a key role in shaping the country's future and development. Supporting and facilitating the social adaptation of youth is becoming one of the priorities of state policy. The desire to improve the system of working with young people is necessary to ensure their

successful development, professional growth, and engagement in active social life. Youth is not only the future of the country but also a current resource capable of making significant contributions to societal development. Therefore, it is essential to develop and implement comprehensive strategies for interacting with young people, ensuring their successful professional and social development [1, pp. 15-18].

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

According to the analysis of available data, since the beginning of 2024, the agency has funded a total of 1,126 young people across the Republic to study professions of the future.

The majority of these young people studied frontend programming - 26.6% (299 people), graphic design - 12% (135 people), backend programming - 9.3% (105 people), Python programming - 6.4% (72 people), and social media marketing (SMM) - 6% (68 people).

When analyzing the training of young people in modern professions by region, Samarkand (221 people), Fergana (182 people) regions and the city of Tashkent (145 people) had higher participation, while Syrdarya (14 people), Bukhara (26 people),

and Jizzakh (29 people) regions had relatively lower participation.

For reference: Within the framework of the “Professions of the Future” project, the majority of young people studied English through IELTS, CEFR (66.1%) or General English (12.9%) courses.

Additionally, over the past years, the Agency has trained more than 20,000 young people in modern professions and foreign languages, of whom 2,571 (2,011 in modern professions, 560 in foreign languages) have started earning income in

their respective fields. For example, young people who have obtained foreign language certificates are more numerous in Fergana (45 people), Navoi (40 people), and Bukhara (33 people) regions.

According to the survey results of 2,014 young people, 46.4% learned programming, 14.7% studied video operation, editing, and mobile photography, 14.3% studied graphic design, 9.8% studied logistics, 9.7% studied SMM (targeted marketing) and copywriting, 2.6% studied PR management, and 2.4% studied HR management (Diagram 1).

Diagram 1

Young people studying modern professions

A study of the problems faced in vocational training for young people revealed that 31.6% of them had qualified teachers who meet the demands of the modern labor market, 21% noted a lack of sources in the Uzbek language for studying modern professions (IT, SMM, web-designer, etc.), 18.5%

noted shortcomings in connecting theoretical knowledge with practice, 16.3% noted a lack of material and technical base for vocational training, and 12.5% noted that labor collectives teach in-demand professions (Diagram 2)

Diagram 2

Problems in vocational training of young people

At a time when there is a lack of Uzbek language resources for modern professions among young people, it is advisable for the state to provide financial support for translating materials in this field.

One in four young people in Samarkand (26.3%),

Fergana (26.2%), Jizzakh, Khorezm, and Bukhara (22.4%) regions supported the idea that there is a shortage of Uzbek language resources for learning modern professions (Diagram 3).

Diagram 3

Lack of resources in the Uzbek language for studying modern professions (IT, SMM, web designer, etc.) young people in favor (%)

Additionally, young people in Andijan (39.8%), Jizzakh (38.6%), and Kashkadarya (38%) regions acknowledged the shortage of qualified teachers

who meet the requirements of the modern labor market (Diagram 4).

Diagram 4

lack of qualified teachers who meet the requirements of the modern labor market

For reference: young people in Syrdarya (14.7%) and Bukhara (16.5%) regions reported that they are being trained in low-demand professions in labor collectives.

It is noteworthy that the lack of material and technical resources for vocational training is one of the main problems facing young people in the Syrdarya (19%) and Surkhandarya (19.9%) regions.

Table 1

Percentage increase in monthly income of young people as a result of vocational training (%)			
1-2 mln	21,9	10-15 mln	5,3
Up to 500 thousand sum	21,3	15-20 mln	3,6
3-4 mln	17,1	25 mln and above	2,7
5-7 mln	11,4	unincreased income (inscribed in other part)	10,1
8-10 mln	6,6		

The following proposals have been put forward to further increase the effectiveness of training young people in professions (modern professions):

Specifically, 27.9% emphasized the need for comprehensive support for specialists teaching

modern professions, 18.8% suggested safe, orderly, and legal deployment of qualified young personnel abroad and ensuring their employment, 14.2% recommended increasing the number of qualified teachers, 11.8% proposed increasing resources,

on modern professions in the Uzbek language (IT, SMM, web design, etc.), and 11.3% stressed the need to strengthen measures for training in high-demand professions.

Among the aforementioned proposals, young people who support strengthening measures to send qualified young personnel abroad and ensure their employment are primarily from Tashkent city (39.2%), the Republic of Karakalpakstan (37.3%), and Samarkand region (33.3%).

A comprehensive and multifaceted approach is needed to improve the system of working with youth. The following strategies can be implemented to enhance outcomes for young people:

1. Strengthening cooperation:

Develop collaboration between government agencies, non-profit organizations, schools, and community stakeholders to create a coordinated and integrated youth support system. By working together, we can leverage resources, share best practices, and provide a wide range of services to meet the diverse needs of young people [2, pp. 207-211].

2. Tailored assistance programs:

Develop and implement customized programs that address the specific needs of young people, including mental health services, career guidance, life skills training, and civic engagement opportunities. These programs should respond to the unique challenges facing young people today and equip them with the necessary tools and resources to succeed.

3. Expanding youth participation:

Create opportunities for active youth involvement in decision-making processes, advocacy, and public initiatives. By giving young people a voice and authority in shaping their future, we can foster a sense of ownership, responsibility, and empowerment among them [2, pp. 51-54].

4. Mentorship and role models:

Establish mentoring programs that connect young people with experienced professionals, mentors, and role models who can guide, support, and inspire them. Mentoring relationships can help young people overcome challenges, set goals, and realize their full potential.

5. Investments in education and employment:

Increase investments in education, vocational training, and workforce development programs to enhance the qualifications, knowledge, and employability of young people. By creating sustainable employment, entrepreneurship, and career advancement pathways, we can equip young people with the tools they need to succeed in a rapidly changing world [3, pp. 35-37].

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

According to the research results, today's youth face difficulties in learning IT and modern professions, as well as in mastering the trades of plumber, electrician, designer, and welder. It is noteworthy that currently, there is a growing global demand for these fields (Canada alone is offering jobs in electrical engineering, plumbing, welding, and several other areas), making it advisable to improve efforts in this regard.

It is also recommended to organize national competitions (best electrician, youngest plumber, most experienced welder, best designer) aimed at identifying the most talented young people in Uzbekistan in these fields, with subsequent targeted work with them. This, on the one hand, will further increase youth interest in learning these professions, and on the other hand, will allow for the identification of skilled young people who have mastered these trades. With the identified talented youth, it will be possible to carry out targeted work in the future, develop projects for them to study foreign languages, and guide them towards higher-paying jobs in developed countries.

According to the research, rural youth experience more difficulties in learning IT and modern professions, as well as in starting their own businesses.

The development of these fields, which are the main source of interest for young people in the modern labor market, is also considered a primary requirement for rural youth. It is necessary to support projects aimed at organizing "offline" courses that enable the study of these professions in rural areas, as well as expanding opportunities for free access to "online" courses for rural youth.

There is a growing interest in the nursing profession among women, and the research results show that women living in the villages of Jizzakh (9.8%), Khorezm (9.9%), the Republic of Karakalpakstan (9.2%), Surkhandarya (9.1%), and Tashkent (9.2%) regions face more difficulties in mastering this profession.

In collaboration with the Ministry of Health and the Agency for Youth Affairs, it is advisable to develop a special platform called "Medical Science," aimed at improving young people's medical knowledge and providing guidance in the field of nursing, primarily focusing on the aforementioned areas.

Indeed, the nursing profession is no less responsible, complex, and honorable than that of a doctor. Attention to these professions is increasing year by year.

It is necessary to increase the number of resources in the Uzbek language (textbooks, videos

on social networks) considering the interest of young people in learning modern professions (IT, SMM, web design, etc.).

It is necessary to establish an annual practice of

rewarding young people who have produced high-quality translations of video content from foreign languages into Uzbek, based on competition criteria and expert evaluations, with a cash prize.

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Annotatsiya: *IUshbu maqolada O'zbekistonda yoshlarni kasbga yo'naltirish va takomillashtirish muammolari ko'rib chiqiladi. Iqtisodiyotning jadal rivojlanishi va mehnat bozorining o'zgaruvchan ehtiyojlarini hisobga olgan holda, yoshlarni tegishli kasblarga yo'naltirishning dolzarbligi alohida ahamiyat kasb etmoqda. Tadqiqotda mavjud kasbiy ta'lim dasturlari tahlili, shuningdek, yoshlarning martaba imkoniyatlari to'g'risida xabardorligini oshirish uchun qo'llaniladigan usul va yondashuvlar o'rin olgan. Kasbga yo'naltirish jarayonida davlat organlari, ta'lim tashkilotlari va tadbirkorlik subyektlarining roliga alohida e'tibor qaratilmoqda. Xulosa qilib aytganda, mamlakatimizning kadrlar salohiyatidan yanada samarali foydalanishga xizmat qiladigan kasbiy maslahat va yoshlarga kasb tanlashda ko'mak berish tizimini takomillashtirish bo'yicha tavsiyalar beriladi*

Kalit so'zlar: *yoshlar, ta'lim, bandlik, yoshlar tashabbuslari, ijtimoiy faollik, mehnat tizimi, kasbiy salohiyat.*

Аннотация: *В данной статье рассматриваются проблемы профессиональной ориентации и совершенствования молодежи в Узбекистане. Особую актуальность приобретает ориентация молодежи на соответствующие профессии с учетом стремительного развития экономики и меняющихся потребностей рынка труда. Исследование включает анализ существующих программ профессионального образования, а также методов и подходов, используемых для повышения осведомленности молодежи о карьерных возможностях. Особое внимание уделяется роли государственных органов, образовательных организаций и субъектов предпринимательства в процессе профориентации. В заключение даются рекомендации по совершенствованию системы профессионального консультирования и содействия молодежи в выборе профессии, что послужит более эффективному использованию кадрового потенциала страны.*

Ключевые слова: *молодежь, образование, трудоустройство, молодежные инициативы, социальная активность, система труда, профессиональная компетентность.*

YOSHLARNI OILAVIY HAYOTGA TAYYORLASHNING PSIXOLOGIK MUAMMOLARI

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Annotasiya: Ushbu maqolada nikoh va oilaviy munosabatlarning barqarorligi yoshlarning oilaviy hayotga tayyorligiga bog'liqligi, turmush qurishga tayyorlik oilaviy turmush tarziga hissiy ijobiy munosabatni belgilaydigan shaxsning ijtimoiy-psixologik munosabatlari tizimi ekanligi bayon etilgan. Hozirgi kunda jamiyatda oilaviy nizolarning soni ortib bormoqda bunga sabablardan biri sifatida yoshlarni oilaviy hayot haqidagi tasavvurlarini yetarli darajada shakllanmaganligini keltirish mumkin. Ushbu maqolada yoshlarni oilaviy hayotga psixologik tayyorlash muammosi bayon qilingan. Oila haqidagi tasavvurlarni shakllantirishga oid sharq mutafakkirlarining qarashlari va zamonaviy yondashuvlar, shuningdek, oila borasidagi ijtimoiy-psixologik masalalar muhokama qilingan.

Kalit so'zlar: Nikoh, oila, tarbiya, munosabatlar, farzand, jamiyat, turmush, oilaviy munosabatlar, yoshlar, ota-ona, shaxs, axloqiy-psixologik tayyorgarlik, qadiriya.

Bugungi kunda O'zbekiston aholisining 62 foizini bolalar, o'smirlar, xullas 30 yoshgacha bo'lgan yigit qizlar, ularning ma'lum qismini esa yosh oilalar tashkil etadi. Yosh oilalar jamiyat ijtimoiy-siyosiy, iqtisodiy, madaniy-ma'naviy yangilanishi va yuksalishini muhim subyektlaridan bo'lib, ijtimoiy hayotda ro'y berayotgan murakkab jarayonlarga o'z ta'sirini o'tkazishda va taraqqiyotni harakatda keltirishida muhim ro'l o'ynaydi. Shuning uchun hozirgi vaqtda yosh oilalarning ma'naviy-axloqiy va ruhiy olamini shakllantirish va rivojlantirishni chuqur va atroflicha tahlil etish ilmiy - amaliy jihatdan katta ahamiyat kasb etadi.

Shu nuqtai nazardan mustahkam oilalarni shakllantirish, onalik va bolalikni ijtimoiy jihatdan muhofaza qilish, oilalarda jismonan sog'lom, ruhan baquvvat bo'lgan farzandlarning dunyoga kelishi uchun qulay shart-sharoitlarni yaratish, samarali ravishda oila tarbiyasini tashkil etish jarayonida oilalar bilan jamoatchilik o'rtasida mustahkam hamkorlikni yuzaga keltirish masalalarini davlat siyosati darajasida e'tibor qaratilmoqda. 1993-yilning fevral oyida "Sog'lom avlod" ordenining ta'sis etilishi hamda "Sog'lom avlod" Davlat dasturi" ning qabul qilinganligi fikrimizning yorqin dalilidir.

Zamonaviy oilaning eng muhim ijtimoiy vazifasi kelajak oila boshlig'ini tarbiyalash, ya'ni yosh avlodni nikoh va oilaviy munosabatlarga tayyorlashdir. Bunga salbiy jarayonlarning kuchayishi: oilaviy turmush tarzining tanazzulga uchrashi, nikoh va

oilaviy munosabatlarning muqobil shakllarining keng tarqalishi, oila obro'sining pasayishi, farzand ko'rish zarurati, ajralishlar va oila ichidagi zo'ravonliklarning ko'payishi sabab bo'lmoqda. Zamonamizdagi oilaviy hayotning eng yaxshi an'analari va yangiliklarini o'zida mujassam etgan yosh, mustahkam oilani barpo etishning dolzarbligi jamiyatning ma'naviy-axloqiy inqirozi va ijtimoiy hayot inqirozidan chiqish yo'lining ajralmas va eng muhim qismidir. Zamonaviy oila-ning eng muhim ijtimoiy vazifasi yosh avlodni nikoh va oilaviy munosabatlarga o'rgatishdir. Nikoh va oilaviy munosabatlarning barqarorligi yoshlarning oilaviy hayotga tayyorligiga bog'liq bo'lib, bu yerda turmush qurishga tayyorlik oilaviy turmush tarziga hissiy ijobiy munosabatni belgilaydigan shaxsning ijtimoiy-psixologik munosabatlari tizimi sifatida tushuniladi. Zamonaviy oilaning eng muhim ijtimoiy vazifasi kelajak oila boshlig'ini tarbiyalash, ya'ni yosh avlodni nikoh va oilaviy munosabatlarga tayyorlashdir. Bunga salbiy jarayonlarning kuchayishi: oilaviy turmush tarzining tanazzulga uchrashi, nikoh va oilaviy munosabatlarning muqobil shakllarining keng tarqalishi, oila obro'sining pasayishi, farzand ko'rish zarurati, ajralishlar va oila ichidagi zo'ravonliklarning ko'payishi sabab bo'lmoqda. Yoshlarning jamiyatdagi mavqei, rivojlanish tendentsiyalari va istiqbollari, avvalambor, uning kelajagini belgilab bergani bilan jamiyat uchun katta qiziqish va amaliy ahamiyatga ega. Bu yerda yoshlarning nikoh va jamiyatning

asosiy bo'g'ini sifatida oilaga munosabati muhim o'rin tutadi. Dunyoning aksariyat qismlarida nikohning o'rtacha yoshi o'sib bormoqda va o'n yil avvalgiga qaraganda, dunyo bo'ylab o'smirlilik davrida kamroq nikohlar sodir bo'lmoqda. Hozirgi vaqtda oilaviy munosabatlarda sezilarli o'zgarishlar ro'y bermoqda.

Yoshlarni psixologik jihatdan oilaviy hayotga tayyorlash va faoliyatning samarali tashkil etilishi bir

qancha ijtimoiy muammolarning ijobiy hal etilishiga o'z ta'sirini ko'rsatadi:

-Jamiyatning ijtimoiy ma'naviy jihatdan rivojlanishini ta'minlaydi;

-jamiyatning ijtimoiy iqtisodiy taraqqiyotining yuqori bosqichga ko'tarilishida muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi;

-mustahkam oilalarni shakllantirish, ularda sog'lom psixologik muhitni qaror toptirish, oila

tarbiyasini samarali tashkil etish, farzandlar tarbiyasida muayyan muvaffaqiyatlarga erishish, oilaviy mojaro, ajrimlarning oldini olish uchun zamin hozirlaydi.

Sharqda yoshlarni oilaviy hayotga tayyorlashga qadimdan jiddiy ahamiyat berilgan. Jumladan Abu Nasr Farobiy, Abu Rayxon Beruniy, Abu Ali ibn Sino, Yusuf Xos Xojib, Kaykovuskiy, Alisher Navoiy, Rizouddin ibn Faxriddin kabi allomalar bu masala yuzasidan o'zlarining durdona fikrlarini tarixda qoldirib ketganlarki, ular hozirgacha o'z ahamiyatini yo'qotmagan. Ular «Nasixatnoma», «Pandnoma», «Xikmatnoma» tarzida bizgacha yetib kelgan. Bu manbaalarda qizlarni hayotga tayyorlashda, ularda birinchi navbatda insoniy fazilatlar shakllangan bo'lishi, oila muqaddas, uni avaylab asrash aynan uy bekalariga bog'liq ekanligi xaqida turli tarbiyaviy ahamiyatga ega bo'lgan xodisalar hikoya qilinadi. «Kaykovuskiy 63 yoshida o'g'liga atab «Qobusnoma» yozib, unda o'zining bola tarbiyasi, oilaviy hayot, shaxs kamoloti masalalarini bayon etdi.

A.Avloniy "Tarbiya biz uchun yo hayot yo

mamot, yo najot-yo halokat, yo saodat-yo falokat masalasidir", degan fikri o'zbekning kun tartibidan tushmasligi lozim. Chunki avvalgiga o'xshab qariyalar keksalar yoshlarni odob axloqqa chaqirib yoshlar esa ularni hurmatlab, ularning o'g'itiga amal qilish udumi yo'qolib bormoqda. Har kim o'zi bilan ovora bironing gapi bironing yoqmaydi. S.V.Kovolyov o'smir va qizlarda oila va nikoh tushunchalari haqidagi tasavvurlarga ega bo'lishlari juda muhimdir, deydi. Nikoh va sevgi tushunchalari 13-15 yoshli bolalarda qarama-qarshi tushunchalar ekanligi bilan kuzatiladi, ya'ni ular sevgi va nikoh bir-biriga teskari tushunchalar ekan deb tushunadilar. Talabalarda umr yo'ldosh tanlashda sevgi tushunchasi faqat 4 o'rinda, ya'ni xurmat qilish, ishonch, bir-birini tushunish kabi xislatlardan keyin turadi. Yoshlar oilani jiddiy qabul qilmaydilar. Natijada juda ko'p xatoliklarga yo'l qo'yib, keyinchalik oilaning muhimligini psixologik tan oladilar. Bizning asosiy vazifamiz shuki, o'smirlarda oilaning qadrini, sevgi, nikoh oiladagi sevgini roli muhimligini va u uzoq va baxtli hayot garovi ekanligini o'qitirishdir.

Ko'pgina mamlakatlarda munosabatlarning yangi

turi tobora keng tarqalmoqda - ro'yxatdan o'tmagan nikoh. Biroq, yoshlarning qadriyat yo'nalishlari bo'yicha olib borilgan tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, oila yoshlar uchun asosiy qadriyat bo'lib qolmoqda. Yoshlar sotsializatsiya jarayonida otionalarning oilasidan yordam va yordam izlaydilar va ular o'zlarining bo'lajak oilasini insonparvarlik va axloqiy tamoyillar asosida qurishga tayyor, lekin shu bilan birga ularda juda katta psixologik bilim va ko'nikmalar yetishmasligi mavjud. Bu asarda yoshlarning oilaviy hayotga tayyorligini shakllantirish muammosining ko'p jihatlari qatorida zamonaviy jamiyatda oila va nikohning ijtimoiy rolini to'g'ri anglash, fuqarolik huquqiy ongining mavjudligi ko'rsatilgan. Binobarin, yoshlarni oilaviy hayotga maqsadli tayyorlash zarurati ham nikoh-oila munosabatlarini yanada rivojlantirish, uning shaxsning har tomonlama barkamol rivojlanishiga xizmat qilishi, ham o'zaro munosabatlarga nisbatan erkaklar va ayollar, oilaviy hayot haqida noto'g'ri qarashlarni bartaraf etish bilan belgilanadi. Pedagog

va psixologlarning ta'kidlashicha, yosh avlodni oilaviy hayotga tayyorlash uning yosh rivojlanishining barcha bosqichlarida amalga oshirilishi kerak va ta'limning umumiy muammolaridan ajralmasdir. Shaxs qismlarga bo'lib shakllanmaydi va bir sohada ta'limning yetishmasligi boshqa sohada uning natijalarini buzadi.

Insonni oilaviy hayotga, ishlab chiqarish faoliyatiga yoki jamoat hayotida faol pozitsiyani egallashga alohida tayyorlash mumkin emas. Oila shaxsning axloqiy va aqliy tarkibini tashkil etuvchi asosiy va ijtimoiy asosdir. Oiladagi psixologik iqlim va uning a'zolari o'rtasidagi munosabatlar har qanday yoshdagi shaxsning ishlab chiqarish faoliyatiga, ijtimoiy vazifalarni bajarishiga, ijodiy qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirishga bevosita ta'sir qiladi. Jinsiy tarbiya, yoshlarni nikoh va oilaviy munosabatlarga tayyorlash dolzarb va murakkab pedagogik muammolardan biridir. Hozirgi zamon oilasining ijtimoiy psixologik muammolarini yoritishga bag'ishlangan psixologik adabiyotlarda nikoh oldi

omillarining turlicha shakllari, ko'rinishlari farqlanadi. Quyida sizning e'tiboringizga ularning ayrimlari haqidagi ma'lumotlarni havola etamiz: Nikoh oldi omillari qatoriga shu oila qurayotgan yoshlarning: oilaviy hayotga yetukligi: ularning oila qurish motivlari: ularning oila qurishgunlariga qadar bir-birlarini tanish muddati (qancha vaqt bir-birini tanishi) shartlari va sharoitlari: ularning o'zlarining bo'lg'usi oilaviy hayotlari haqidagi tasavvurlari kabilarni kiritish mumkin. Albatta, bu omillarning har bir turli yoshlarda turlicha harakterda bo'lishi mumkin, shu bilan birga ularning har biri o'z navbatida yana bir necha turlarga farqlanadi. Masalan, nikohga yetuklik deyilganda oila quruvchi

yoshlarning jismoniy (fiziologik), jinsiy, huquqiy, iqtisodiy, ma'naviy-axloqiy, psixologik kabi yetuklik jihatlarni farqlash mumkin. Bularning orasida huquqiy, jinsiy yetuklik ko'rsatkichlari yetarlicha aniq alomatlarga, belgilarga ega bo'lgan va bular haqida tegishli huquqiy, tibbiy, psixologik adabiyotlarda ko'plab ma'lumotlar berilgan jihatlar bo'lsa, iqtisodiy, ma'naviy-axloqiy, psixologik jihatlar biroz murakkabroq, qat'iy bir ko'rsatkich, chegaraga ega emasligi bilan harakterlanadi. Masalan, odamning jinsiy yetukligi o'ziga xos omillarga ega. Klinik kuzatishlar ma'lumotlariga ko'ra, hozirgi zamon qizlarida jinsiy yetuklik (balog'atga yetish) 12-14 yoshgacha, o'g'il bolalarda esa 14-16 yoshga to'g'ri

keladi. Albatta, bu yetuklik ba'zi bir bolalarda ertaroq, boshqa birlarida kechroq ro'y berishi mumkin. Bu ko'rsatkichlar ± 2 yoshga farq qilishi mumkin.

Bugungi kunda O'zbekiston aholisining 62 foizini bolalar, o'smirlar, xullas 30 yoshgacha bo'lgan yigit qizlar, ularning ma'lum qismini esa yosh oilalar tashkil etadi. Yosh oilalar jamiyat ijtimoiy-siyosiy, iqtisodiy, madaniy-ma'naviy yangilanishi va yuksalishini muhim subyektlaridan bo'lib, ijtimoiy hayotda ro'y berayotgan murakkab jarayonlarga o'z ta'sirini o'tkazishda va taraqqiyotni harakatda keltirishida muhim ro'l o'ynaydi. Shuning uchun hozirgi vaqtda yosh oilalarning ma'naviy-axloqiy va ruhiy olamini shakllantirish va rivojlantirishni chuqur va atroflicha tahlil etish ilmiy - amaliy jihatdan katta ahamiyat kasb etadi.

Oila tarbiyasi jamiyatda yosh avlodni tarbiyalash shakllaridan biri sifatida, V.A. Suxomlinskiyning fikricha, ota-onalarning, barcha oila a'zolarining maqsadli harakatlari va kundalik hayot va oilaviy munosabatlarning bolalarga ob'yektiv ta'sirini o'z ichiga oladi. O'qituvchi bolalarning oilaviy tarbiyasi tajribasini tahlil qilib, "Ota-onalar va bolalar o'rtasidagi mavjud munosabatlarga ega oila birinchi intellektual, axloqiy, estetik va jismoniy tarbiya maktabi ekanligini" ko'rsatdi. V.A. Suxomlinskiyning chuqur ishonchiga ko'ra, oila bolalarda axloqiy tuyg'ularni singdirishning asosiy maktabi bo'lishi kerak va bu axloqiy g'oyalari va tushunchalarni shakllantirish, axloqiy tuyg'ularni rivojlantirish, axloqiy e'tiqodlarni rivojlantirish, xulq-atvor ko'nikmalarini va odatlarini shakllantirishni anglatadi. Nikohgacha ta'limga katta hissa qo'shgan V.A. Suxomlinskiyning aksariyat hollarda nikohning asosiy motivi "sevgi" deb hisoblagan. Biroq, "sevgi" ni nikoh motivi sifatida ataganda, yoshlar bu so'zga turli xil ma'nolarni qo'yishadi. T.A. Florenskaya bu so'zning uch xil tushunchasini belgilaydi: sevgi - jinsiy jalb qilish; sevilish zarurati sifatida sevilish; dominant sifatida sevgi. Nikoh haqida gapirganda, nikoh ittifoqiga kirish istagi va unga kirishga tayyorlik darajasi bir xil tushunchalardan uzoq ekanligini unutmasligimiz kerak. Psixologlarning fikricha, shaxsning turmush qurishga axloqiy-psixologik tayyorgarligi oila hayotini tartibga soluvchi talablar, majburiyatlar va xulq-atvorning ijtimoiy standartlari butun majmuasini idrok etishni anglatadi. Bularga quyidagilar kiradi:

- turmush o'rtog'ingiz, bo'lajak farzandlaringiz oldida yangi mas'uliyat tizimini qabul qilishga tayyorlik va ularning xulq-atvori uchun javobgarlik;
- oila ittifoqining boshqa a'zolarining huquq va qadr-qimmatini anglash, insonlar o'rtasidagi munosabatlarda tenglik tamoyillarini tan olish;
- har kungi muloqot va hamkorlikka intilish, qarama-qarshi jins vakili bilan o'zaro munosabatlarni

muvofiglashtirish, bu esa o'z navbatida yuksak axloqiy madaniyatni nazarda tutadi;

- boshqa odamning odatlari va xarakter xususiyatlariga moslashish va uning ruhiy holatlarini tushunish qobiliyati. Bunday yetuklikka bir kechada erishilmaydi va ko'plab omillarga bog'liq. Birinchi omil er va xotinning, keyin esa ota va onaning rollarini bajarish uchun psixologik tayyorgarlik va qobiliyatga bo'lgan ehtiyoj. Har bir ijtimoiy rol o'z ijrochisiga qo'yiladigan ma'lum umidlarni o'z ichiga oladi. Shuning uchun, er va xotin bo'lishga tayyor bo'lish, bu umidlar (ya'ni, huquq va majburiyatlar) haqida aniq bo'lishni va ularni bajarishga tayyor bo'lishni anglatadi. Psixologik tayyorgarlikdan tashqari, oilaning eng muhim tarkibiy qismlari erkak va ayol o'rtasidagi funktsional rol munosabatlaridir. Oilaning roli, birinchi navbatda, bolada turmush o'rtog'i sifatida umumiy qabul qilingan xulq-atvor me'yorlariga nisbatan yo'nalishlar va munosabatlar to'plamini shakllantirishdir. Xususan, bu o'zini ma'lum bir jins vakili sifatida identifikatsiya qilish, er va xotin o'rtasidagi o'zaro munosabatlarni belgilaydigan jamiyatda mavjud bo'lgan hayotiy qadriyatlarni qabul qilishdir. Bundan tashqari, bolalikdanoq yaqinlar haqida hissiy va hissiy idrok etish stereotiplari shakllana boshlaydi. Psixologlar va sotsiologlar tomonidan olib borilgan ko'plab tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatdiki, yigit va qizlarning kelajakdagi oilaviy hayoti haqidagi g'oyalari ota-onalar oilasida o'z-o'zidan shakllanadi - uni takrorlash istagi yoki hamma narsani boshqacha qilish istagi sifatida. Oila an'anaviy ravishda o'smir shaxsining ijtimoiy ahamiyatga ega qadriyatlari va munosabatlarini shakllantirish va rivojlantirish va uning ijtimoiylashuvida yetakchi ijtimoiy institut bo'lib qolmoqda. Oilani sotsializatsiya qilishning asosiy usuli - bu bolalar kattalar oila a'zolarining xatti-harakatlarini nusxalashdir. Ijtimoiylashuvdagi qiyinchiliklar, agar bola boshqa oilalarda ko'rgan narsaga zid bo'lgan ota-onaning noto'g'ri, g'ayrioddiy xatti-harakatlari bilan boshqarilsa, paydo bo'ladi. Oilada o'rganilgan ma'lumotlar jamiyatda qabul qilingan qadriyatlar va me'yorlardan farq qilishi va hatto ularga zid bo'lishi mumkin. Oila, qoida tariqasida, o'zining ijtimoiy va qadriyat yo'nalishini shakllantiradi, u bolalarga o'tadi.

Oilaning xulq-atvori va ijtimoiy me'yorlari bir-biriga zid bo'lmagan taqdirda, shaxsni shakllantirish jarayoni nizolansiz davom etadi. Bugungi kunda yosh avlodni ijtimoiylashtirishning eng faol davri iqtisodiy va siyosiy beqarorlik va an'anaviy qadriyatlarning parchalanishining og'ir sharoitlarida sodir bo'ladi. Shuning uchun ijtimoiy o'zgarishlar sharoitida oila yangi qadriyatlar va xulq-atvor normalarini shakllantirishning samarali vositasi bo'lishga chaqiriladi.

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Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается связь стабильности брака и семейных отношений с готовностью молодежи к семейной жизни. Утверждается, что готовность к браку — это система социально-психологических отношений личности, определяющая позитивное эмоциональное отношение к семейной жизни. В настоящее время в обществе наблюдается рост числа семейных конфликтов, одной из причин чего является недостаточная сформированность представлений молодежи о семейной жизни. В статье изложена проблема психологической подготовки молодежи к семейной жизни. Обсуждаются взгляды восточных мыслителей на формирование представлений о семье, современные подходы, а также социально-психологические проблемы, связанные с семьей.

Ключевые слова: Брак, семья, воспитание, отношения, дети, общество, жизнь, семейные отношения, молодежь, родители, личность, морально-психологическая подготовленность, ценности.

Annotation: This article discusses the relationship between the stability of marriage and family relationships and the readiness of young people for family life. It explains that readiness for marriage is a system of social-psychological relations of an individual, which determines a positive emotional attitude toward family life. Currently, the number of family conflicts in society is increasing, and one of the reasons for this can be attributed to the insufficient development of young people's perceptions about family life. The article addresses the issue of psychologically preparing young people for family life. It discusses the views of Eastern thinkers on shaping concepts of family life, modern approaches, as well as social-psychological issues related to family

Keywords: Marriage, family, upbringing, relationships, children, society, life, family relationships, youth, parents, individual, moral-psychological preparedness, values.

ZAMONAVIY JAMIYATDA YOSH OILALARNING MILLIY AXLOQIY QADRIYATLARI

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Yoshlar muammolarini o'rganish va istiqbolli kadrlarni tayyorlash instituti Mustaqil izlanuvchisi (PhD)

Annotasiya: Ushbu maqolada yosh oilalarning milliy axloqiy qadriyatlarini, ularning rivojlanishida to'sqinlik qilayotgan omillar, oilalarining o'ziga xos xususiyatlari, yosh oilalardagi ijtimoiy munosabatlar va ularning taraqqiy etishiga ta'sir etuvchi omillar haqida so'z yuritiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: yosh oila, qadriyat, nikoh, yoshlar, zamonaviy jamiyat, rivojlanish

Kirish: Inson hayoti va farovonligining asosini oila va oilaviy qadriyatlar tashkil etadi. Har bir shaxsning ma'naviy-axloqiy fazilatlarini shakllanishida, shubhasiz, oila muhim o'rin tutadi. Bugungi kunda zamonaviy yosh oilalarning ustuvor yo'nalishlari mustaqillik va o'zini o'zi hissiy anglash tashkil etadi. Oila qurish yoshlar tomonidan yaxshi niyatlar ila rejalashtirilgan hodisa bo'lib, yoshlar ushbu holatni faqat muvaffaqiyatli bosqich deb biladilar.

Mavzuning dolzarbligi: Zamonaviy ilmiy adabiyotlarda oilaning asta-sekin jamiyatda ta'lim va rivojlanish kabi asosiy funksiyalarini o'rni sezilarli pastlagani haqida tez-tez aytiladi. Oqibatda yosh avlodning oila qurishning ahamiyati to'g'risida ma'naviy-axloqiy tushunchalari yetarli emasligini alohida ta'kidlashimiz mumkin, chunki bu ularning zimmasiga katta mas'uliyat yuklaydi.

Mamlakatimiz yosh oilalarni qo'llab-quvvatlash, yangi ijtimoiy loyihalarni ishlab chiqish, ko'p bolali oilalar turmush darajasini oshirish, yoshlarga qaratilgan tibbiyotni rivojlantirish borasida zarur va tizimli ishlarni amalga oshirib kelmoqda. Jumladan: 2017-yil 5-iyuldagi PF-5106-son "Yoshlarga oid davlat siyosati samaradorligini oshirish va O'zbekiston Yoshlar Ittifoqi faoliyatini qo'llab-quvvatlash to'g'risida"gi, 2020-yil 30-iyundagi PF-6017 sonli "O'zbekiston Respublikasida yoshlarga oid davlat siyosatini tubdan isloh qilish va yangi bosqichga olib chiqish chora-tadbirlari to'g'risida"gi, 2021-yil 13-iyuldagi PF-6260 sonli "Yoshlarni har tomonlama qo'llab-quvvatlash va ularning ijtimoiy faolligini yanada oshirishga oid qo'shimcha chora-tadbirlar to'g'risida"gi farmonlari, O'zbekiston Respublikasi Vazirlar Mahkamasining 2019-yil 11-sentabrdagi

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Bularning barchasi mamlakatda demografik ko'rsatkichlarning oshirishga, zamonaviy yoshlarning oilaga bo'lgan qarashlarini o'zgartirishga, yosh oilalarni ijtimoiy qo'llab-quvvatlashga, shuningdek, ularning farovonligini oshirishga xizmat qiladi.

Mavzuga oid mavjud muammolar: Bugungi kunda zamonaviy jamiyatning dolzarb muammolaridan biri demografik hodisa bo'lib, bu yoshlarning oila va nikoh qurish haqidagi qarashlarining o'zgarishi bilan bog'liq¹. Yoshlarning oilaviy qadriyatlar haqidagi tasavvurlari ular tug'ilgan oila va jamiyat ta'sirida shakllanadi. O'g'il bolalar qizlardan barcha an'anaviy ayollik majburiyatlarini bajarishlarini kutishadi, qizlarning o'zi esa bo'lajak turmush o'rtoqlaridan faol ijtimoiy hayotga sodiq bo'lib, mas'uliyat taqsimotini kutishadi. Oila ijtimoiy institutning ajralmas, hayoti-mizning esa asosiy qismlaridan biridir, chunki shaxsiyat aynan shu kichik ijtimoiy guruhda shakllanadi.

Rossiyalik mashhur olim S.N. Volkovning nazdida har bir yosh avlod dastlabgi qadriyatlarini oilada shakllantirishi va oiladan andoza olishi haqida quyidagicha izoh bergan: "Inson birinchi muloqot qobiliyatini oilada rivojlantiradi, uning shaxsiyatini

¹ "Посысов Н.Н. Основы психологии семьи и семейного консультирования / Н.Н. Посысов. - М.: Книга по Требованию, 2019.

oilada shakllanadi va har qanday milliy qadryati, an'ana va urf-odatlarini oiladan o'tadi, shuningdek, hatto kichik o'zgarishlar ham inson hayotining davlat va umuman jamiyat sohalarida o'zgarishlardan dalolat beradi" – deya o'z fikrini bayon etgan².

Shubhasiz, hozir nikoh yoshi o'zgarib bormoqda, lekin bu oila qurish istagiga ta'sir qilmaydi, ammo yoshlar o'z munosabatlarini qonuniylashtirishga ya'ni nikoh qurishda tayyor bo'lish shartlari o'zgarib bormoqda. Boisi zamonaviy yoshlarning katta qismi oilaviy hayot farovonligining zaruriy tarkibiy qismi sifatida moddiy bazaga ega bo'lish, o'zi uchun qulay muhit (uy-joy, mashina, kasb-hunar, biznes) ga ega bo'lishni "kelajakga" ishonch garovi deb biladi. Bu ijobiy hodisa hisoblanadi, chunki moliyaviy barqarorlikka ega bo'lgan yosh oilalar qo'shma uy xo'jaligini yanada muvaffaqiyatli boshqarish imkoniyatiga ega bo'ladi. Bu pozitsiyaning salbiy tomoni ham bor - mamlakatimizdagi barqaror iqtisodiy vaziyat tufayli moddiy boyliklarni to'plash uzoq vaqt davomida cho'zilishi va bu, o'z navbatida, to'laqonli oilani yaratish jarayonini kechiktiribgina qolmay, bu aholining ko'payishi, mamlakatimizning demografik holatiga salbiy ta'sir ko'rsatadi.

Dunyodagi demografik vaziyatga zamonaviy jamiyatda yuz berayotgan oila va nikoh institutining inqirozi salbiy ta'sir ko'rsatmoqda, bu ertami-kechmi tug'ilishning keskin pasayishiga va o'limning oshishiga olib kelishini dunyo davlatlari misolida ham ko'rishimiz mumkin.

Keling endi qadriyat tushunchasi, ma'no va mazmuni haqida to'xtalib o'taylik.

"Qadriyat — voqeilikdagi muayyan hodisalarning umuminsoniy, ijtimoiy axloqiy, madaniy ma'naviy ahamiyatini ko'rsatish uchun qo'llanadigan tushuncha³. Oilaviy qadriyat esa oila uchun ahamiyatli bo'lgan ijtimoiy tenglik, haqiqat, yaxshilik, go'zallik, moddiy va ma'naviy boyliklar, an'ana, urf-odat va boshqalar oilaviy qadriyatlar hisoblanadi. Umuman olganda qadriyatni biz turli ko'rinishda ko'rishimiz

mumkin. Jumladan:

Milliy qadriyatlar – ma'lum bir millat, elat yoki xalqning asrlar davomida shakllangan, jamiyatning ma'daniyati, turmush tarzi, urf-odat va an'analari, shuningdek, o'tmishi va kelajagiga bog'liq bo'lgan qadriyatlar milliy qadriyatlar hisoblanadi;

Umuminsoniy qadriyatlar – insoniyat uchun muhim bo'lgan, jamiyatning eng muhim tomonlarini ifodalaydigan, asrlar davomida o'z ahamiyatini yo'qotmagan ozodlik, tinchlik, erkinlik kabi umumbashariy xususiyatga ega bo'lgan qadriyatlar umuminsoniy qadriyatlardir;

Shaxsiy qadriyatlar – shaxs uchun uning faoliyati, e'tiqodi, umr ma'nosi sifatida qaralgan, har bir kishining o'zi ulug'laydigan qadriyati shaxsiy qadriyat hisoblanadi.

Bugungi kunda zamonaviy jamiyatda yosh oilalarning qadriyatlari tez sur'atlarda o'zgarib bormoqda, chunki jamiyatning iqtisodiy, ijtimoiy va madaniy sharoitlari o'zgarmoqda. Bu jarayon yosh oilalar va ularning qadriyatlari, turmush tarzini, qarashlarini shakllantiradi. Zamonaviy yosh oilalarining qadriyatlari quyidagi asosiy yo'nalishlar bo'yicha o'zgarishlarni ko'rsatadi:

1. Oila tuzilmasidagi o'zgarishlar:

a) Oila shakllari va roli – zamonaviy yosh oilalarida oila tuzilmasi o'zgarib bormoqda. An'anaviy kattalar, ota-onalar va bolalar o'rtasidagi aloqalar o'zgarmoqda. Ba'zi oilalarda erkaklar va ayollar o'rtasidagi rollar tenglashgan, ya'ni ayol ham oilaning iqtisodiy jarayonlariga faol hissa qo'shadi;

b) Turmush o'rtoqlar o'rtasidagi hamkorlik – ko'plab yosh oilalarida hamkorlik asosida qarorlar qabul qilinadi, bu esa oilaviy munosabatlarni yanada mustahkam qiladi.

2. Ma'naviy va diniy qadriyatlar:

a) Din va ma'naviyat – ba'zi yosh oilalar diniy qadriyatlarni saqlashga harakat qilmoqda, lekin diniy ta'limotlar va an'anaviy marosimlar yosh oilalar orasida kamayib bormoqda;

b) Ma'naviy qarashlar – ko'plab yosh oilalar o'zlarining ma'naviyati va ruhiy salomatligini saqlashga harakat qilmoqdalar. Bu ko'proq ruhiy tarbiya va o'ziga nisbatan hurmatni rivojlantirishga yo'naltirilgan.

3. Erkak va ayol o'rtasidagi tenglik:

a) Gender tengligi – bugungi kunda yosh oilalarda erkak va ayol o'rtasidagi rollar va mas'uliyatlar tenglashtirilmoqda. Ayollar ko'proq ish kuchiga kirishmoqda va oiladagi qarorlar qabul qilishda erkaklar bilan teng huquqlarga ega bo'layotganini ko'rishimiz mumkin;

b) Ish bilan oila muvozanati – ayollar va erkaklar o'rtasida mehnat va oilaviy majburiyatlarni

² Волков С.Н., Саратовцева Н.В. История педагогики и философия образования. - Пенза: Изд-во. ПензГТУ, 2014.

³ <https://uz.wikipedia.org/wiki/Qadriyat>

muvozanatlash ko'proq yosh oilalarda uchraydigan holatdir.

4. Iqtisodiy qadriyatlar:

a) Iqtisodiy erkinlik – yosh oilalar o'zlarining iqtisodiy erkinligini ta'minlashga intilmoqda. Ayollar va erkaklar o'rtasidagi iqtisodiy mas'uliyatlar teng taqsimlanmoqda, bu esa oilaning iqtisodiy barqarorligini ta'minlaydi;

b) Mehnat va moliyaviy jihatlar – yosh oilalar o'zlariga turli manbalarni yaratishga intilmoqda, bu esa o'z kelajagiga sarmoya kiritishning bir qismidir.

5. An'anaviy qadriyatlar va zamonaviylik o'rtasidagi qarama - qarshiliklar:

a) An'anaviy va zamonaviy qadriyatlar o'rtasidagi nizolar – ba'zi yosh oilalar an'anaviy qadriyatlar bilan zamonaviy dunyoqarash o'rtasida qarama-qarshiliklarga duch kelmoqda. Bu o'zgarishlar oilaviy munosabatlarda noaniqlik, qarama-qarshiliklar yoki kelishmovchiliklarga olib

kelishi mumkin.

Muammoni hal qilish usullari: Shuni aytib o'tish joizki, bugungi kunda yoshlarni jumladan, yosh oilalarni jamiyatdagi qadriyatlarni ulug'lash, e'zozlashga doir quyidagi ishlarni amalga oshirish lozim deb bilaman:

- yoshlarda ijtimoiy institutning asosi hisoblangan oila va oilaviy qadriyatga asoslangan munosabatni shakllantirish maqsadida "Ustoz" soatlarini tashkil etish;
- oilaviy an'analar haqida davra suhbatlari, ma'naviy-ma'rifiy targ'ibot tadbirlarini ko'proq tashkil etish;
- yoshlarda oilaviy qadriyatlarni e'zozlashga va to'g'ri munosabatni shakllantirishga qaratilgan videoroliklarni ishlab chiqish va namoyish etish kabi ishlarni amalga oshirish lozimdir.

Zamonaviy jamiyatda yoshlar o'rtasida oila nufuzini mustahkamlash va oilaviy qadriyatlarga mos tarbiyalash bo'yicha biz ko'rib chiqqan barcha yo'nalishlarni darhol amalga oshirish imkoni mavjud

emas. Kichik yoshdagilardan boshlab va asta-sekinlik bilan bir yo'nalishdan ikkinchisiga o'tish, bosqichma-bosqich amalga oshirish maqsadga muvofiqdir.

Ishonchimiz komilki, tizimdagi aniqlangan muammolarni har qanday yo'l bilan bartaraf etish mumkin, chunki davlat bu boradagi muammolarni qanchalik samarali va tez hal etsa, butun jamiyat uchun shunchalik yaxshi va foydalidir.

Oila ma'naviy va madaniy qadriyatlarning tashuvchisi bo'lib, axloqiy ideallar va xulq-atvor namunalarning manbai bo'lib xizmat qilgan. Aynan oila shaxsning yoshligidanoq asosiy fazilatlarini shakllantiradi, birlamchi qadriyatlarni, ideallarni, axloqiy me'yorlarni shakllantiradi, axloqning ilk saboqlarini beradi va shu orqali shaxsning to'liq shakllanishini ta'minlaydi. Oila ijtimoiy institut sifatida jamiyatning barqaror rivojlanishini ta'minlaydi, ijtimoiy hayotning ko'plab jarayonlari va hodisalariga tartibga soluvchi ta'sir ko'rsatadi hamda jamiyatimizning samarali va har tomonlama rivojlanishiga yordam beradigan bir qator boshqa muhim funktsiyalarni bajaradi. Ijtimoiy institut sifatida oilaning asosiy maqsadi, eng avvalo, nasl tug'ilishi va bola tarbiyasi, axloqning asosiy ijtimoiy normalarini avloddan-avlodga yetkazish, shu orqali asosiy muloqot qobiliyatlarini va insonning ijtimoiylashuvining muvaffaqiyatli jarayonini ta'minlashdir.

Yoshlarning qarorlari sog'lom fikr va mulohazaga asoslanadi. Ammo salbiy tomoni shundaki, yosh avlodning hayotiy maqsadlarida mehnat, martaba va ta'lim birinchi o'rinni egallaydi. Bundan tashqari, so'nggi o'n yilliklarda nikoh yoshini oshirish va oilani yaratishni keyingi hayotga qoldirish tendentsiyasi aniq kuzatilmoqda. Shuningdek, so'nggi paytlarda ko'p kuzatilyotgan yosh oilalarda uchraydigan moliyaviy nochorlik, uy-joy muammosi, bandlik va tibbiy yordam, yosh turmush o'rtoqlarning bir-biriga moslashishi va yangi sharoitlardan iborat psixologik muammolar kabi jiddiy muammolar bilan bog'liq.

Biroq, ishonch bilan aytish mumkinki, oilalar buzilishining katta foizi ko'plab ijtimoiy jarayonlarga salbiy ta'sir qiladi, mamlakat iqtisodiyotini sekinlashtiradi va demografik inqirozning chuqurlashishiga yordam beradi.

Yangi turmush qurgan oilalar butun oilaga xos bo'lgan ko'plab muammolarni boshdan kechirishadi. Shu bilan birga, yosh oilalarda ijtimoiy qo'llab-quvvatlashga ehtiyoj katta, chunki ko'pchilik jiddiy ijtimoiy muammolar, uy-joy, ishsizlik va shaxsiy muammolarni boshdan kechirmoqda. Bugungi kunda yoshlarning reproduktiv munosabatlarini to'liq ro'yobga chiqarish ham ko'p jihatdan davlat, jamiyat va keksa avlod vakillari tomonidan o'z vaqtida moddiy va ma'naviy qo'llab-quvvatlanishiga bog'liqdir.

Bunday mushtarak tarbiya asosida avlodlar vorisligi yotmog'i lozim. Vorislikni ta'minlashning muhim omili oila qadriyatlariga asoslanishdan iboratdir. Eng muhimi, yoshlar ongiga, shuuriga kattalarga hurmat, ishda, o'qishda odamlar bilan munosabatda ota-onadan o'rnak olish, tarbiya, mehnat, insonparvarlik, vatanparvarlik qadriyatlarini chuqurroq o'rganish va ularga amal qilish, umrboqiyiligini ta'minlashdek muhim ishni amalga oshirish bugungi kunda ijtimoiy ehtiyojga aylanib qolmog'iga erishish zarur.

Ilmiy asoslangan taklif va tavsiyalar: Shunday qilib, yoshlar qatlami qadriyatlarini o'zida aks ettiruvchi ma'lum bir hal qiluvchi omil bo'lib, unga butun jamiyatning rivojlanishi va to'liq faoliyati bog'liqdir. Zero, inson mavjudligining asosi oiladir. Binobarin, yoshlarda oila qurishga jiddiy munosabat, nikoh to'g'risidagi to'g'ri g'oyani shakllantirish, oilaviy

qadriyatlarga e'tiborli munosabatni shakllantirish zarur.

Yosh oilalarning qadriyatlari odatda ularning farovon va mustahkam oila qurishga intilishlariga asoslanadi. Biz ham yosh oilalarning jamiyati va madaniyatiga qarab ularning milliy va axloqiy qadriyatlarini yuksaltirish maqsadida quyidagi takliflarni ilgari suramiz:

1. Ishonch va halollik – yosh oilalar o'zaro ishonch va ochiqlikka katta ahamiyat berishlari va oila a'zolari bir-birlariga nisbatan halol va ochiq munosabatda bo'lish orqali o'z oilalarini mustahkamlaydilar;

2. O'zaro hurmat va qo'llab-quvvatlash – o'zaro hurmat, bir-birini tushunish va qo'llab-quvvatlash yosh oila a'zolari orasidagi muhim

qadriyatlardan biri bo'lishi kerak. Bu esa oiladagi munosabatlarning sog'lom va barqaror bo'lishiga katta hissa qo'shadi;

3. Mas'uliyat – yosh oilalar farzand tarbiyasi, moliyaviy ta'minot va oila farovonligi uchun mas'uliyatni to'liq tushunib, uni qadrlashlari hamda ularda mas'uliyat hissi jamiyatda o'z vazifalarini vijdonan bajarishiga yaqindan yordam beradi.

4. Tenglik va sheriklik – ko'pgina yosh oilalar erkak va ayol o'rtasidagi tenglik va hamkorlikni qadrlaydilar. Ular qaror qabul qilishda birgalikda ishtirok etishi va uy ishlarini teng bo'lishini ta'minlashga intilishlari zamonaviy yosh oilaning asosiy qadriyatiga aylanmog'i zarurdir;

5. Sog'lom turmush tarzi – sog'lom turmush tarzi, shu jumladan sog'lom ovqatlanish va jismoniy faoliyat ham ko'pincha yosh oilalar uchun qadrlanadi, chunki bu oila a'zolarining salomatligi va hayot sifatini oshiriga o'z ta'sirini ko'rsatadi;

6. Farzandlar tarbiyasi – ko'plab yosh oilalar farzandlarining yaxshi ta'lim olishi, axloqiy rivojlanishi uchun alohida ahamiyat qaratishi lozim. Bu esa yosh oilalar uchun muhim qadriyat bo'lib qolishi maqsadga muvofiqdir;

7. Ta'lim va o'z-o'zini rivojlantirish – yosh oilalar uchun shaxsiy rivojlanish va ta'lim olishi, ular o'zlarining bilim va ko'nikmalarini oshirishga intilishlari ham qadriyat sifatida shakllanishi darkor. Bularning barchasi yosh oilaning umumiy muvaffaqiyati uchun muhim hodisadir.

Oilada yosh avlodni ota-ona namunasi, oila an'analari, shajarasi, kasb-kori, axloqiy-ma'naviy qadriyatlari asosida tarbiyalash, ular ongida oilaga sadoqat, o'zaro mehr-muhabbat, hurmat hissini shakllantirish vositasida ularni oilaviy hayotga tayyorlash kutilgan natija beradi. Bu qadriyatlar oila a'zolari o'rtasida mustahkam munosabatlar o'rnatishga, o'zaro ishonch va hurmatni saqlashga yordam beradi va oilaning yanada baxtli hayot kechirishi uchun asosiy rol o'ynaydi.

Xulosa o'rnida shuni ta'kidlab o'tmoqchimanki, yoshlarga oid zamonaviy oila siyosatini shakllantirishda asosiy e'tiborni yosh oilalarning nikoh xulq-atvoridagi asosiy qarama-qarshiliklarni bartaraf etishga qaratish, oila ijtimoiy institutini mustahkamlashga yangicha yondashuvlarni innovatsion qarashlarni olib kirish zarur.

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Аннотация: В данной статье говорится о ценностях молодых семей, факторах, препятствующих их развитию, особенностях их семей, социальных отношениях в молодых семьях, факторах, влияющих на их развитие.

Ключевые слова: молодая семья, ценности, брак, молодежь, современное общество, развитие.

Annotation: This article talks about the values of young families, the factors hindering their development, the characteristics of their families, social relations in young families, and the factors affecting their development.

Keywords: young family, value, marriage, youth, modern society, development.

YANGI O‘ZBEKISTON SHAROITIDA YOSHLAR FAOLLIGINI OSHIRISH VA ULARNING MA’NAVIY ASOSLARINI MUSTAHKAMLASH ISTIQBOLLARI

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Annotasiya: mazkur maqolada O‘zbekistonda yoshlarni faollashuv jarayonlarini ma’naviy asoslarini mustahkamlash omillari haqida so‘z boradi. Bugungi kunga kelib yer yuzidagi aholining ko‘p qismini tashkil etadigan yoshlar har bir jamiyatning xazinasidir, agar ularni imkoniyatlari to‘g‘ri yo‘naltirilsa. Respublikamizda yoshlar imkoniyatlari keng yo‘lga qo‘yilganligi ular faoliyatini to‘g‘ri tashkil etilganligini isbotidir.

Kalit so‘zlar: : yoshlar, inson kapitali, milliy taraqqiyot, Uchinchi Renessans, ma’naviyat, ma’rifat, milliy o‘zlik, milliy qadriyatlar, demokratik qadriyatlar, islohotlarga daxldorlik, ta’lim tizimi, Yangi O‘zbekiston.

Kirish.

Uchinchi ming yillikka kelib dunyo aholisini qariyb 2 milliardini yoshlar tashkil etadi. Bu esa o‘z o‘rnida dunyoda inson kapitali hamda innovatsion salohiyatni rivojlantirishda yoshlar imkoniyatlaridan to‘g‘ri va samarali foydalanish, shu bilan birga yoshlar faolligini oshirishning ma’naviy asoslari masalalarida nodavlat notijorat tashkilotlarining ulushi ortib borayotganligini ko‘rsatadi. Bu jarayonlar yoshlar faolligini oshirish mexanizmlari bo‘yicha jiddiy tadqiqotlar amalga oshirilishini taqozo etadi.

Jahonning bir qator rivojlangan mamlakatlarida bugungi kunda yoshlar faolligini oshirish borasida yirik ilmiy tadqiqot markazlari ish olib boradi. Xususan, Junior Chamber International (JCI) (Amerika), Nisseikyo (Yaponiya), Asunaro (Janubiy Koreya) kabi yoshlar tashkilotlari faoliyatlarini misol keltirish mumkin. Yoshlarda sog‘lom dunyoqarashni shakllantirish zamonaviy ilm-fan yutuqlarini milliy qadriyatlar bilan uyg‘unlashtirgan holda amalga oshirish shu tashkilotlarning amaliy faoliyatlarini rag‘batlantirib boradi. Birlashgan millatlar tashkilotida “Yoshlar huquqlari to‘g‘risidagi xalqaro Konvensiya”¹ ishlab chiqish taklifi berilganligi ham

bejiz emas. Dunyo davlatlarda nodavlat notijorat tashkilotlarining huquq va vakolatlarini ta‘minlanishi, fuqarolik jamiyati prinsiplarini to‘la amal qilinishi mazkur yo‘nalishda ilmiy tadqiqot ishlarini olib borish zaruratini yanada oshiradi.

O‘z milliy taraqqiyot yo‘lini tanlagan O‘zbekistonda yoshlarni har tomonlama qo‘llab-quvvatlash bo‘yicha katta ishlar olib borilmoqda. “Yangi O‘zbekiston, bu sog‘lom, bilimli va ma’naviy barkamol insonlar yurtidir”² – deb ta’kidlar ekan, bu O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining siyosiy irodasi mamlakatda ilm-fan, madaniyat, ma’rifat va ma’naviyatni yanada yuksaltirish yo‘lida chuqur islohotlarni boshlab berganligining ifodasidir. Bu esa o‘z o‘rnida mamlakat tarixida Uchinchi Renessansni boshlanishiga turtki bo‘ldi. O‘zbekistonda ta’lim, fan va innovatsiya sohalarini rivojlantirishga nodavlat notijorat tashkilotlarini keng jalb etilayotgani xalqaro siyosiy platformaga to‘la mos keladi.

Asosiy qism.

Yoshlarning yangi zamonaviy ma’naviy qiyofasini shakllantirish bugungi O‘zbekiston siyosatini mazmunini tashkil etmoqda. Shu bois, davlat yoshlarda ularning investitsion va innovatsion xarakterini

¹ O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining BMT Bosh Assambleyasining 72-sessiyasida taklif etilgan.

² Bizning maqsadimiz aniq va o‘zgarasdir – demokratik davlat va fuqarolik jamiyati qurish yo‘lini yanada qat’iy davom ettiramiz. Sh.M.Mirziyoyevning tadbirkorlar va ishbilarmonlar harakati – O‘zbekiston liberal-demokratik partiyasining XI s‘ezdidagi nutqi. XXI asr. Ijtimoiy siyosiy gazeta. 31-may 2023 yil.

kuchaytirishi, uni amalga oshirishda esa preventiv tarzda maxsus dasturlar tizimini joriy etishni taqozo etmoqda. Shu nuqtai nazardan, yoshlar yangi institutsional texnologiyalarni takomillashtirish, yoshlar bilan ishlash tizimlarini kuchaytirishda yoshlar bilan ishlaydigan kadrlarning metodik va uslubiy jihatdan maxsus bilimlarga ega bo'lishini talab etadi. Yoshlar bilan ishlash tamoyillarini kuchaytirish ijtimoiy investitsiyalarni jalb etish, yoshlarning innovatsion rivojlanishini ta'minlash, ularning tashabbusidan unumli foydalanishni taqozo etadi.

Yoshlar bilan ishlashning barcha zamonaviy uslublarini milliy manfaatlar asosida qayta shakllantirib, amaliyotga joriy etish dolzarb muammodir. Bugungi kunda yoshlar qatlamining o'zida turfa xillik, manfaatlar xilma-xilligi kuzatiladi. Ana shu rang-baranglik asosida har bir yosh uchun ish uslublarini to'g'ri belgilash, uni demokratik qadriyatlar ruhiyatida tarbiyalash yoshlarni begona g'oyalardan asrashning samarali uslublaridan biri hisoblanadi. Shu bois, yoshlar bilan ishlashda:

- omma bilan hamkorlikning mavjud barcha yangi usullarini qo'llash;
- ma'naviyatni yuksaltirish texnologiyalari va omma tafakkuriga ta'sir etishning yangi uslublaridan unumli foydalanish;
- yoshlar qiziqishlari va tafakkurining o'sish tendensiyalarini chuqur o'rganish asosida ularni davlat ravnaqi uchun muhim bo'lgan maqsadlarga yo'naltirish;
- demokratik qadriyatlar erkinlik, tenglik, hurfiylik, qonun ustuvorligi, shaxsiy va jamoatchilik manfaatlari, davlat boshqaruvida ishtirok etish, fuqarolik mas'uliyati, o'z manfaatlarini jamoat hamda davlat manfaatlari bilan uzviy bog'lay olish qobiliyati kabilarning amaliy qo'llanilishiga erishish;
- yoshlar bilan ishlashda asosiy e'tiborni jamiyatdagi birdamlik, barqarorlik, o'zaro ishonch va hamkorlik usullariga qaratish;
- yoshlar bilan ishlaydigan kadrlarga bo'lgan talabni kuchaytirish;
- yoshlar bilan ishlashda ularning ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy ahvoli bo'yicha ma'lumot va dalillar to'plash, ularni tahlil qilish, axborotlarni yoshlarga ta'sirchan usulda yetkazish;
- yoshlar bilan ishlashda hamfiylik, ochiqlik, oshkorlik, muammoli mavzulardan qo'rqmaslik, tenglik, shaffoflik tendensiyalarini amaliy qo'llash;
- yoshlar bilan ishlashda yoshlar qatlamlariga nisbatan differensial munosabatni shakllantirish, yangi pedagogik texnologiyalar tizimi, yakka tartibda, guruhlar, omma bilan ishlash usullaridan foydalanish, shuningdek, interfaol usullarni keng

joriy etish bugungi davlat tashkilotlari va muassasalarining yoshlar bilan ishlash bo'g'inlariga mas'uliyat yuklaydi.

Yoshlar va davlat orasida bevosita vertikal va gorizontal muloqot, ya'ni axborot kommunikatsiyalari hamda shaffoflikni joriy etish ular o'rtasida ishonch va yangilanishlarga aloqadorlik hissining ortishiga xizmat qiladi. "...axborot kommunikatsiya texnologiyalari qanchalik rivoj topgani sari, uning afzalligi va qulayliklaridan foydalanish bilan bir qatorda, butun mamlakatimizda axborot xavfsizligini ta'minlash eng dolzarb masalaga aylanib bormoqda"³.

Yoshlarda islohotlarga daxldorlikni shakllantirishda yangilanish va vorisiylik tamoyillarining qisqa tahlili davlatimizning yoshlarga oid siyosati hayotning barcha sohalaridagi keng qamrovli islohotlar, jamiyatdagi tub o'zgarish jarayonlari bilan bog'liq ravishda amalga oshmoqda. O'zbekiston o'z taraqqiyotining yangi bosqichiga qadam qo'yar ekan, yoshlarga oid davlat siyosati ularni ijtimoiy himoyalash, demokratik va fuqarolik jamiyati barpo etishning faol ishtirokchilariga aylantirish, huquq va manfaatlarini ta'minlash, turli sohalaridagi imkoniyatlarini yanada kengaytirish kabi masalalarni hal qilishga yo'naltirildi. Shu asnda, yoshlarga jamiyat rivojida "portlash" effektini vujudga keltiruvchi omil, mamlakat kadrlar zahirasini shakllantiruvchi asosiy kuch, kelajakka qaratilgan bunyodkorlik faoliyatida tayanch va suyanch sifatida qarash an'anasi shakllandi. Bugungi kunda yoshlarda islohotlarga daxldorlikni shakllantirishda yangilanish va vorisiylik tamoyillarini barqaror qilishga qaratilgan yoshlar siyosati mamlakatimizda demokratik islohotlarni yanada chuqurlashtirish va fuqarolik jamiyatini rivojlantirish maqsadlari bilan uzviy aloqadorlikda amalga oshirilmoqda.

Yangi O'zbekiston tajribasi shundan dalolat beradiki, o'tgan yillar davomida jamiyatimiz hayotining barcha sohalarida amalga oshirilayotgan islohot natijalari, xalq ma'naviyatining tiklanishi, boy, milliy tarixiy merosimizning keng o'rganilishi, an'analarning asrab-avaylanishi, madaniyat va san'at, fan va ta'lim ravnaqi yoshlarga oid siyosat samaradorligini oshirish masalalari bilan uzviy bog'liqdir. Bu sohalaridagi islohotlar va ularning bugungi kundagi yuksak natijalari ushbu siyosatning samarali amalga oshirishini ta'minlashga qaratilgan nafaqat iqtisodiy, siyosiy omillar, balki ma'naviy asoslarning ham nihoyatda mustahkam zaminga tayanishini yaqqol ko'rsatib turibdi.

Bugungi zamon shiddati inson hayotida ma'naviyatni naqadar muhim ekanligini taqozo etmoqda. Zero, axloqsizlik, odobsizlik, ma'naviy qashshoqlik

³ Mirziyoyev Sh.M. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti lavozimiga kirishish tantanali marosimiga bag'ishlangan Oliy Majlis Palatalarining qo'shma majlisidagi nutqi. Xalq so'zi. 2016 yil 15 dekabr

insonni tubanlik girdobiga giriftor etib, keng miqyosda esa jamiyat taraqqiyotini izdan chiqarib, parokandalikni yuzaga keltiradi. Ma'naviyat yo'qolgan joyda insonda hayvoniy hislatlar ildiz otib, yovvoyilik, vahshiylik, jaholat va xurofot kuchayadi. Natijada inson o'z aslini yo'qotish orqali qadriyat sifatidagi maqomidan judo bo'ladi.

Shu bois, ota-bobolarimiz qadimdan bebaho boylik bo'lmish ma'naviyat va ma'rifatning yoshlar tarbiyasi, inson kamoloti va millat ravnaqining eng asosiy shartlaridan biri deb, bilganlari bejiz bo'lmagan. "Hujjatul Islom" Imom Abu Homid al-G'azzoliy "Kimyoi saodat" asarida ta'kidlaganidek: "Inson farishta va hayvon orasidagi mahluqdir. Hayvon rivojlanmaydi, chunki uning kamolot quvvati yo'q. Farishta ham rivojlanmaydi, chunki uning o'zi pok ilohiy nurdan iborat, chunki insonlardagina rivojlanish, ruhiy kamolot hislati mavjud"⁴.

Shu bilan birga bugungi kunda quyidagi vaziyatlarga alohida ahamiyat berish zarurati ortib bormoqda:

- mamlakatimizda mavjud bo'lgan ta'lim tizimining barcha bosqichlarida ta'lim olayotgan va hunar o'rganayotgan yoshlarni yuksak ma'naviy qadriyatlarga sodiqlik hissi va bu boradagi tamoyillarni amalga oshirishda faollik tuyg'ularini tarbiyalashga alohida e'tibor qaratish;

- nafaqat talabalar, balki bu vazifani amalga oshirishning eng muhim bo'g'ini bo'lgan barcha ta'lim muassasalaridagi ustoz-murabbiylarning ma'naviyat sohasidagi savodxonligini yanada oshirish, ularning bu sohada butun jahonda ro'y berayotgan voqea-hodisalar va respublikamizda amalga oshirilayotgan tub islohotlarning natijalari bilan tezkor va izchil tanishtirishga mo'ljallangan ommaviy axborot vositalari faoliyatini samarasini oshirishga alohida ahamiyat berish;

- ta'lim tizimi bilan qamrab olinmagan yoshlar qatlamlari orasiga yuksak ma'naviyat tamoyillarini singdirish, targ'ib va tashviq etish samaradorligini muntazam oshirib borish mexanizmlarini yanada takomillashtirish, bu sohada zamonaviy texnologiyalardan foydalanish imkoniyatlarini yanada kengaytirish;

- joriy yil uchun mo'ljallangan davlat dasturida nazarda tutilgan vazifalarni bajarish doirasida amalga oshiriladigan faoliyat jarayonida yoshlarga doir davlat siyosatining ma'naviy omillari ta'sirchanligini oshirishga xizmat qiladigan chora va tadbirlarga alohida e'tibor qaratish.

Yurtimizda huquqiy davlat va rivojlangan fuqarolik jamiyati asoslarini yaratilayotganligi bugungi kun uchun nihoyatda muhim, chunki yuksak ma'naviyat demokratik taraqqiyotning zaruriy asosi,

ma'nau barkamol avlod shakllanayotganining muhim ko'rsatkichi hisoblanadi. O'z navbatida, mamlakatimizda bozor munosabatlarining chuqurlashuvi, demokratik-huquqiy davlat va erkin fuqarolik jamiyatining rivojlana borishi bilan bugungi ijtimoiy rivojlanishning yangi bosqichiga mos yoshlarni tarbiyalab voyaga yetkazish, ularda davr talablariga xos ma'naviy qiyofasi va zamonaviy tafakkurini shakllantirish masalalari yanada dolzarblashib bormoqda.

Mamlakatimizda jismonan sog'lom, ma'naviy va intellektual jihatdan yetuk, mustaqil fikrga ega bo'lgan avlodni voyaga yetkazish va tarbiyalash, ularni har tomonlama qo'llab-quvvatlash va rag'batlantirish davlat siyosatining ustuvor vazifalaridan biri sifatida e'tirof etilgan. Iqtidorli yoshlarni rag'batlantirish, ularning ta'lim sohasidagi huquq va manfaatlarini himoya qilish yuzasidan amalga oshirilayotgan ishlar ham ana shu jabhadagi faoliyatning muhim tarkibiy qismi hisoblanadi. Bu borada Prezidentimiz Shavkat Mirziyoyev qayd etganidek: "Biz yoshlarga doir davlat siyosatini hech og'ishmasdan, qat'iyat bilan davom ettiramiz. Nafaqat davom ettiramiz, balki bu siyosatni eng ustuvor vazifamiz sifatida bugun zamon talab qilayotgan yuksak darajaga ko'taramiz"⁵.

Bu nuqtai nazardan, hozirgi davrda yuksak bilimli, zamonaviy fikrlaydigan, intellektual rivojlangan va professional tayyorgarlikka ega bo'lgan yoshlarga butun dunyoda, jumladan mamlakatimizda ro'y berayotgan jadal innovatsion taraqqiyotning eng yuksak talablariga javob bera olishi mumkin. Ana shunday yoshlarga mamlakatning buyuk kelajagini ta'minlashi, mustaqillikni asrab-avaylash va uni mustahkamlashning muhim sharti va garovi sifatida o'z vazifasini bajarishga qodir avlod bo'lishi mumkin.

Hozirgi davrda O'zbekiston yoshlarning bevosita huquq va erkinliklarini ta'minlashga qaratilgan 30 dan ortiq xalqaro huquqiy hujjatlarining ishtirokchisi hisoblanadi. O'zbekiston Respublikasi BMTning yosh avlodning huquq va erkinliklarini ta'minlashga oid universal ahamiyatga ega bo'lgan muhim hujjatlarini ratifikatsiya qilgan. Inson huquqlari umumjahon Deklaratsiyasi, Bola huquqlari to'g'risidagi Konvensiya, Fuqarolik va siyosiy huquqlar to'g'risidagi xalqaro pakt, iqtisodiy, ijtimoiy va madaniy huquqlar to'g'risidagi xalqaro pakt, irqiy kamsitishning barcha shakllariga barham berish to'g'risidagi xalqaro konvensiya va boshqa huquqiy hujjatlar shular jumlasidandir. Shu bilan birga, O'zbekiston YUNESKO va Xalqaro Mehnat Tashkiloti tomonidan qabul qilingan muhim konvensiyalarning ishtirokchisi ham sanaladi. Mamlakatimizda yosh-

⁴ Abu Homid G'azzoliy. Kimyoi saodat. -Toshkent.: Adolat. 2005. B29

⁵ Sh.Mirziyoyev. Milliy taraqqiyotimizni qat'iyat bilan davom ettirib yangi bosqichga ko'taramiz. Toshkent – "O'zbekiston" - 2017. B146

larni qonuniy huquq va manfaatlarini himoya qilish, ularning huquqiy va siyosiy madaniyatini oshirish, o'z hayotiy pozitsiyasi hamda mustaqil qarashlariga ega bo'lgan barkamol avlodni voyaga yetkazish O'zbekiston siyosatini tashkil etadi.

Xulosa.

Har bir davlat o'z siyosatini amalga oshirish borasida yoshlar qatlamini tayanchi va istiqbolni belgilab beruvchi asos hisoblanadi. Yoshlar davlatning eng muhim insoniy qadriyatlaridan biri. Yosh avlod vakillarining hayot strategiyasi turli-tumandir. Ular ham mazmuniga ko'ra, ham ularning yetuklik darajasiga ko'ra, ham voqeligiga ko'ra, ham vaqt qamroviga ko'ra farqlanadi. Yoshlar o'zining bo'lg'usi kasbiy faoliyatiga va oilasiga bir muncha real qaraydi. Ayni vaqtda yoshlarning ta'lim olish imkoniyati, ijtimoiy yuksalish va moddiy farovonlik darajasiga da'volari ancha kuchlidir. Yosh insonlar hamma narsaga birdaniga va juda jadal erishishni xohlaydi. Biroq ushbu har xil da'volarning yuksak darajasi doimo ham xuddi shunday yuksak intilishlar bilan mustahkamlanavermaydi. Shuning uchun zamonaviy qadriyatlarga asoslangan ma'naviy-huquqiy yangilanish jarayonlarini amalga oshirish dolzarbligicha qolmoqda.

Yoshlar orasidagi faol fikrlovchilarini yoshlarni rag'batlantirish orqali ular amalga oshirishi mumkin bo'lgan jamiyatni rivojiga ijobiy ta'sir ko'rsatadigan tadbirlarni muntazam tashkil etib borish zaruriyatini keltirib chiqaradi.

Yoshlar manfaatlarini ifodalaydigan tashkilotlarni o'z faoliyatlarini yangi yo'nalishlari ustida yanada ko'proq ishlashlari kerakligini ko'rsatadi.

Mahalla faollariga yondoshgan holda oilalar bilan hamkorlik tizimini joriy etish. Bu tizimni mazmun-mohiyatida bu o'z o'rnida milliy urf-odatlardagi o'ziga xoslikni ifodalaydi.

Yoshlarga oid davlat siyosatining ijtimoiy-

iqtisodiy, ma'naviy ma'rifiy, mafkuraviy-g'oyaviy va siyosiy jihatlarini amalga oshirishda nodavlat notijorat tashkilotlari faoliyati bilan bog'liqligini ta'minlash.

Yoshlarni ish bilan ta'minlash muammosi o'zida bir necha xususiy, ijtimoiy va mamlakat iqtisodiy-siyosiy tuzumidagi islohotlar jarayonlari bilan bog'liq xususiyatlarni namoyon qiladi. Ular:

- mamlakat aholisining yarmidan ko'pi yoshlardan iborat ekanligini hisobga olgan holda yoshlarga mo'ljallangan ish joylarining yetishmasligi, aholining aksariyat qismi qishloqlarda istiqomat qilishi;

- iqtisodiyotning o'ziga xos sohalar bo'yicha bo'linishi, industrial rivojlanish darajasi, qo'l mehnatiga bo'lgan talabning kattaligi, iqtisodiyotning intellektual va yangi ilmiy texnologiyalar bilan bog'liq emasligi, mehnat sharoitini zamonaviylashtirish;

- yoshlarga mo'ljallangan ish joylarining son va sifat nuqtai nazaridan talab darajasida emasligi, yoshlarning ish joylariga bo'lgan ehtiyojlari doirasidagi mehnat motivatsiyalari;

- yoshlar o'rtasidagi mavjud ijtimoiy va hayotiy talablarning mehnat imkoniyatlaridan yuqori ekanligi, ish haqining yoshlar zamonaviy ehtiyojlarini qoplay olmasligi. Ushbu vazifalarni amalga oshirish Yangi O'zbekiston taraqqiyot Strategiyasining to'rtinchi yo'nalishi "Adolatli ijtimoiy siyosat yuritish, inson kapitalini rivojlantirish" yonalishida ham aniq belgilangan. Jumladan, "El-yurt umidi" jamg'armasi orqali erkin va ijodiy fikrlaydigan yoshlarni nufuzli xorijiy oliygohlarga o'qishga yuborish ko'lamini 2 baravarga oshirish, bunda yoshlarning 50 foizini texnik, aniq fanlar va IT sohalarida o'qitish orqali Yangi O'zbekiston sharoitida yoshlar faolligini oshirish va ularning ma'naviy asoslarini mustahkamlash istiqbollari ta'minlanayotganligini ko'rish mumkin.

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Аннотация: в данной статье говорится о факторах укрепления духовных основ процессов активизации молодежи в Узбекистане. Сегодня молодежь составляющая большинство населения Земли, является сокровищем любого общества, если правильно использовать ее возможности. Тот факт, что возможности молодежи в нашей республике широко открыты, является свидетельством того, что их деятельность организована должным образом.

Ключевые слова: молодежь, человеческий капитал, национальное развитие, Третье Возрождение, духовность, просвещение, национальная идентичность, национальные ценности, демократические ценности, участие в реформах, система образования, Новый Узбекистан.

Annotation: this article discusses the factors that strengthen the spiritual foundations of youth activation processes in Uzbekistan. Today, young people, who make up the majority of the world's population, are the treasure of every society, if their opportunities are properly directed. The fact that youth opportunities are widely available in our republic is proof that their activities are properly organized.

Keywords: youth, human capital, national development, Third Renaissance, spirituality, enlightenment, national identity, national values, democratic values, participation in reforms, education system, New Uzbekistan.